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Tommy YC WONG (editor-in-chief)
Zhixing MEI
Yoyo PY TSANG
Nuo XU

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Preface

FLaP FIRST is, in many ways, a wonderful anomaly.

It is a student-led journal devoted to formal linguistics and philosophy, built without funding, free of charge for both authors and readers, and open in both access and spirit. It is a space where reviewers can be openly acknowledged (if they so desire), where their intellectual labor is visible, valued, and published alongside the work it helps shape. In a landscape where academic publishing often feels inaccessible, opaque, or extractive, *FLaP FIRST* is a small but deliberate attempt to do things differently: to confront longstanding problems not merely with critique, but with action, action grounded in the belief that academic publishing can be more open, more equitable, and more humane.

This second volume reflects the richness and diversity of inquiry that such a space can foster. The contributions gathered here range widely: from ethical variation across human societies (Lian Hee WEE), to the intricacies of Cantonese syntax (Tommy Tsz-Ming LEE); from moraicity of sonorant geminates in Tamil (Sampath Kumar SRINIVAS), to tonality in Zuoquan “Rù” (Kaixin ZHAO) and nasal codas in Chinese (Pauline Bolin LIU), to coda stop voicing in Hong Kong English (Philip Chung YEUNG). At first glance, these topics may seem disparate. Yet, as the naturalist John Muir reminds us, “*When we try to pick out anything by itself, we find it hitched to everything else in the Universe.*” What emerges across these pages is precisely this sense of interconnectedness—a shared pursuit of understanding the structures underlying language, thought, and human experience.

This volume would not exist without the trust and dedication of its contributors.

To the authors and reviewers:

Thank you for entrusting your work to *FLaP FIRST*. Your efforts, rigorous, thoughtful, and generous, are what give this journal its life.

To the editorial team:

Thank you for your care, perseverance, and for working through probably countless evenings (which I hope were filled with laughter, eating, and good company).

To the advisory board:

Thank you for your guidance and steady support. Your role, though often less visible, has been essential in shaping and sustaining this wonderful initiative.

It is our hope that this work does more than stand on its own. May it inspire others to participate, to question, and to build. If *FLaP FIRST* represents anything, it is the belief that students can help reshape the norms of academic publishing, not through abstraction alone, but through sustained effort, collaboration, and vision.

With this, we are pleased to present the second volume of *FLaP FIRST*.

Joanna Ut-Seong Sio
Chair, *FLaP FIRST* advisory

The editorial board would like to thank the following people for their expertise as reviewers (in alphabetical order):

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We are unable to give a complete list of the many teachers and friends who have helped and guided us. We are grateful to them all.

In joined hands, sincerely,
Tommy YC Wong
Zhixing Mei
Yoyo PY Tsang
Nuo Xu

Variability in the Manifestation of Universal Laws

Lian-Hee Wee

Hong Kong Baptist University

lianhee@hkbu.edu.hk

Abstract

In attempting to model ethics variation across human societies, the essay argues that universality of natural ethical laws is entirely possible by grounding them on evolutionary biological pressures that ensure the passing of genes. The paper demonstrates that the interaction of these natural laws through prioritization or strength assignment can be parameterized by cognitive distance with the self at the center. To the extent that this modelling is successful, one expects the emergence of morality even if a genetic catastrophe should befall humanity.

Keywords: Universality, Mathematics, Ethics, Biology, Linguistics

1. Preamble: Biology as a stepping stone

This article is primarily concerned with two issues. Firstly, is it possible to calculate ethical judgments and predict ways of resolving ethical conflicts within formal frameworks? Secondly, what kinds of empirical facts would require different formalisms such as parameter setting, prioritization and strength assignment?

At the onset, let me assume that there are some **biological and environmental fundamentals** that influence or constrain ethical laws (if ethical laws can at all be constructed). Note that I am not taking a position for biological or environmental determinism, rather, I am saying that biology and the physical environment wherein we live do **influence and motivate** our ideas about ethics. Hence I assume that there is **biological or environmental motivation** for ethics. One such fundamental is stated below.

- (1) Every organism seeks to maximize chances of its survival through the passing of its genes.

The fundamental in (1) above has been convincingly explained in Dawkins (1976). Despite (1), ethical laws¹ are still necessary because not all the information contained in ethical prescriptions is predictable from (1). However, ethical prescriptions that arise may vary only to the extent constrained by (1), stated as (2).

- (2)
 - a. The rise or inception of ethics/ethical prescriptions is motivated by (1).
 - b. Ethical prescriptions should be maximally consistent with (1).
 - c. Should there be conflicts between ethical prescriptions, the solution maximally consistent with (1) wins.

Given a sufficiently large set of ethical prescriptions, there are bound to be conflicts between these prescriptions in certain situations. Hence, (2c).

¹ I make a distinction between ethical prescriptions and ethical laws. The prescriptions are what the elders of the village or the leaders of religions prescribe, whereas laws are those constructed by scientists studying the patterns of those prescriptions/set of prescriptions.

2. Ethical laws and their interaction: A peek at adultery

To illustrate the interaction of ethical laws and how a suitable framework should provide for conflict resolution, consider the scenarios in (3).

- (3) i. When Ada went into Bob's room and found him in bed with Cindy, Ada was offended. Ada hurled abuse angrily at Cindy. Cindy quickly apologized and left the room. Everybody agreed that Ada did the right thing.
- ii. Three years later, Ada went into Bob's room and found him in bed with Cindy again. This time Cindy was offended. Ada quickly apologized to Cindy and left the room. Everybody agreed that Ada did the right thing.

Given (3), a few questions immediately arise.

- (4) i. When Ada went into Bob's room, why did Ada hurl angry abuse at Cindy when Cindy was in bed with Bob but apologized to Cindy for a similar situation three years later?
- ii. Why did everybody, including Ada, agree that Ada was doing the right thing in both situations?
- iii. Why did Ada have to apologize to Cindy in (3ii)?

The reader might have guessed that in (3i), Bob was married to Ada. In (3ii), Ada had divorced Bob. But, why should being married to Bob justify Ada's hostile reactions against Cindy, while not being married to Bob would require Ada to apologize to Cindy? An explanation for this situation would be one that explains the recurrent prohibitions on adultery.

I begin with (4iii). Hurling abuse at another person may trigger a fight. At the very least, offensive behavior costs potential friendship. Since humans do well with the help of other humans, unlike leopards, offending others is a bad idea. Hence,

(5) Ethics universal²

Law A: Do not make enemies.

It should be clear that (5) is motivated by (1). Making enemies jeopardizes one's chances of survival or even the chances of survival of one's offspring. Enemies would not help you in need and the vindictive would threaten your life and your family. Law A is a very powerful law. Under ordinary circumstances, Cindy would not go to bed with Bob even if she liked him. Law A explains (4iii), but not (4i).

However, given (1), one would expect men to have sex freely and hence produce as many babies as possible. (Here and elsewhere in this essay, see Diamond 1997.) If Bob could produce enough sperms to impregnate all the women in the world, he would want to do so, since that would maximize the survival of his genes by passing them on to as many babies as possible. So, (1) explains why Bob is unfaithful.

Women on the other hand, can at most produce only one baby a year. Infidelity for women would therefore not make too much sense unless their husbands are too often unavailable. Alternatively, for reasons such as the sterility or ill-health of the husband, a

² These ethics universals are not those that are prescribed by any community. These are the laws that a scientist postulates so that he can calculate the exact moral prescriptions of any community.

woman may need to find a better alternative in the gene pool. Consistent with (1), women must want their husbands to be available to them only and not other women, even during pregnancy. This ensures that the economic output (including food, medicine, money, energy, and domestic help) obtained by the man is invested in her and her offspring maximally. The more a man contributes to a particular woman and her child, the better chance of survival of that child and hence the woman's genes. The conflict is thus between the man's maximally spreading his genes and the woman's maximally ensuring the survival of hers. (1) partially explains the anger of Ada in (3i) that could lead to divorce.

To explain why Cindy would go to bed with Bob even though Cindy knew that Ada would be offended, we need again to appeal to (1). To ensure the survival of her genes, a woman must be careful who should sire her offspring. Remember that she can only produce one each year, and each production drains her of energy and increases her death-risk. Many women die of difficult delivery. Hence, if Cindy was convinced that Bob could bring enough food for her and her child, she would choose to sleep with him. Ada probably married Bob for the same reasons.

It could well be that since Bob had gone to bed with Cindy, Ada was no longer confident that Bob can provide for her and Cindy. So, she would leave him. The competition between Cindy and Ada over Bob would explain Ada's anger in (3i).³ When Ada is no longer married to Bob, it no longer matters who Bob slept with. So (5) applies and Ada apologizes to Cindy in (3ii).

The above account is oversimplistic. For example, what if Bob and Ada had children? What if Cindy were barren? The reader may also criticize the writer for dehumanizing 'love' and other moral issues, reducing them into mere animal instincts. Had the writer talked to Ada, Ada probably would say things like what Bob did was morally wrong. I agree that the issues here are moral issues, and my demonstration is that these moral issues have biological (and environmental) motivations. They are not entirely metaphysical. With these motivations, humans developed moral codes and systems. What I have tried to show is the biological motivation for prohibitions against adultery. With (1), other ethics universals such as (6) below are motivated.

(6) Ethics universals

- a. Law B: You shall produce children.
- b. Law C: You shall provide your best for your children.

Law C explains why the better food-providers are chosen as mates. Given (5) and (6), we can predict the behavior of Cindy, Ada and Bob in (3) and (4). Depending on who is married to whom, we can predict if Ada will be angry. Depending on how many eligible males are available to Cindy, we can predict if Cindy will commit adultery with Bob. (More on eligibility later).

Typically, Law A is most powerful. Most people would not copulate with a married person even if that person were a great food-provider. This means that Laws B and C are more often violated than Law A. Using prioritization, we have,

- (7) Law A >> Law B ; Law C
, where $x \gg y$ means x is prioritized over y .

³ While the role of sexual pleasure is a relevant point for this scenario, I am deliberately omitting it for now. Obviously, an adequate analysis must account for cognitive variables too since there are many who have casual sex at the risk of fatal diseases or use contraceptives which, apparently, are violations of law A.

The prioritization in (7) explains why human societies typically prohibit adultery. One does not offend another by copulating with the person's spouse. However, it does not explain why Cindy would violate Law A and sleep with Bob; neither does it explain why Ada would hurl angry abuse at Cindy. We will need a more powerful formalism to calculate the behavior of Cindy and Ada. To do this, we need to assign strength to the various laws. Let me assume something like (8).

- (8) a. Strength of **Law A** is **0.7**.
- b. Strength of **Law B** is **0.4**.
- c. Strength of **Law C** is **0.5**.

With (8), (7) becomes unnecessary. Depending on how Laws B and C couple, their combined strength may override Law A. The ensuing paragraphs examine a few situations that will trigger coupling of the laws. This will allow a more nuanced prediction in the behavior of Cindy and Ada, and will also predict the distribution of polyandrous, polygynous, and monogamous societies.

(9) Various initial conditions set by the environment

- Situation I: There are very few **eligible** male humans available. By eligible, I mean "in control of sufficient factors of production". A feudal lord controls many factors of production, while the peasant does not.
- Situation II: There are very few female humans available but plenty of males. Food is abundant.
- Situation III: There are as many male humans as females. Food is scarce.
- Situation IV: There are as many male humans as females. There is an abundance of food.

Even though one can try to change the environment, the conditions in (9) are largely inviolable.

Situation I

In situation I, Bob is a very powerful feudal lord. **Laws B and C would couple together to overcome Law A**. Their combined strength is 0.9. This coupling is triggered by the situation. Cindy will risk everything and go sleep with Bob. Ada, on the other hand, would still be angry with Cindy, but she will not divorce Bob. We hence predict polygynous societies to be in places where resources are fairly scarce and where those resources are available only to a few males. Polygynous societies should also exist in economies where factors of production are controlled by a minority of males (e.g. Arab countries, Medieval China).

Situation II

In this situation, Cindy will not sleep with Ada's husband, Bob. There are enough eligible men to go around. In fact, a society which finds itself in this situation will be polyandrous. Laws A-C would hardly interact in this situation for the women. One predicts that Cindy and Ada will have many husbands. In fact, we also predict that they may copulate with a few men over consecutive nights so that no man will know whose child she is carrying (see Diamond 1997 for original insight). So, Ada for example, would sleep with Bob on Monday, Dick on Tuesday, Eric on Wednesday, and so on. Neither Bob, Dick, nor Eric would know if they were the father of Ada's child. Since it is equally probable that Ada's child is their child, they will all provide for it. By sleeping with many men, Ada fulfills Law C. By providing for that child, Bob, Dick,

and Eric are trying to fulfill Law B. Had they known that the child belonged to someone else, they would cease provision for the child since it does not help in passing on their genes. That a male will not provide for a child that is not his is motivated by (1). I will state it as Law D.

(10) Ethics universal

Law D: Do not waste your energy.

For male humans in situation II, Law D is in conflict with Law C. The males are uncertain whether they should provide for the child. If the child belonged to someone else, then the male would have violated Law D by providing for it. If it were his, then by not providing, he would violate Law C. Also, by not providing for the child, the child is most likely to die. In that case, it would violate Law B too. Note that in most primitive societies, humans do not usually die from predation, but from infant mortality. This is still true for many underdeveloped countries. However, Law D is a very powerful law. No one I know is willing to work hard for nothing and almost everyone I know is lazy to the extent that they will not use valuable energy on worthless enterprises. I will assume Law D to have the following strength.

(11) **Strength of Law D is 0.6.**

For men in situation II, Laws B and C would couple and overcome Law D. I do not know of any modern human society that is like situation II. Certain species of spiders do indeed have very few females, but they do not live in societies.

Situation III

Given this situation, one would predict a polyandrous society pretty much like the one mentioned in situation II. The reason for this is that having a few males providing for a child and the mother would give the child a greater chance of survival than if a male should provide only for his children. When food is scarce, the male may not find food every day. Instead, he may only be successful in finding food perhaps one out of a few expeditions. If a few males shared in food provision, there would be greater stability in the supply of food. However, biologically, no male would want to waste his energy to feed a child who does not carry his genes. The strategy the female could take would then be one similar to that in situation II. In this case, Laws B and C would also couple to overcome Law D. That will force the males into settling for polyandry.

Societies with situation III are thus likely to be found in mountainous countries where food is fairly scarce and agriculture almost impossible (e.g. the Tre-ba tribe in Tibet).

Situation IV

The Ada-Cindy conflict presented in (3) is most like situation IV. With an abundance of food, there will be a lot more eligible males. Women have greater freedom of choice over the qualified food-provider for their child. In this situation, Laws B and C are not in conflict with Law A. The female does not need to offend others to find the best food-provider for the child. For Cindy to choose to commit adultery and offend Ada, there must be compelling reasons, including, perhaps, ignorance of the fact that Bob is married.

Since other men are available, Ada could well divorce Bob and find better and more faithful options. This is in accordance with Laws B and C. Ada's violent reaction to Cindy's stealing Bob could then be viewed as an attempt to drive Cindy out of the picture, hence preserving the status quo. If Bob does not repent, then Ada would no longer be confident that Bob is the best available and would then divorce him. Preserving the status quo is in accordance with Law D. In this situation, we also see how the ethical laws govern an individual, like Cindy

or Ada. The judgments on whether what Ada did is right or wrong come from the ethical laws that govern the society in which they live. I will not probe too deeply into the distinction between the ethical laws that govern an individual and those that govern society.

However, in a society characterized by situation IV, Cindy and Bob's behavior would be unacceptable. Such a society would be monogamous.⁴ We would predict that such a society would exist in developed countries or places with some amount of equality in who controls the factors of production. Most modern societies are of this type.

The above discussions of hypothetical situations have provided explanations for the questions in (12).

- (12) i. Why did Ada hurl abuses at Cindy in (3i)?
- ii. Why did Bob commit adultery with Cindy?
- iii. Why did Cindy commit adultery with Bob?
- iv. Why did Ada divorce Bob?
- v. Why would Ada apologize to Cindy the next time she found Cindy in bed with Bob?
- vi. Why did society agree with what Ada did?

The behavior of Ada and Cindy is explained by the interaction of the Laws A-D. The way their behavior will be judged by society is given by the interaction of those laws, e.g. in situation IV. The account tacitly assumes a distinction between ethical laws that govern the human species, ethical laws that govern a society, and ethical laws that govern an individual. In Mohanan (1997), he refers to such situations as ethical dilemmas.

The analysis of the Ada-Cindy conflict shows that law prioritization is inadequate, and that weight assignment offers a more powerful calculus. This is because law prioritization cannot account for ganging up effects, as in the coupling of Laws B and C to overcome other more powerful laws, such as Laws A or D. In most scenarios, Laws B and C do not couple to overcome Law A. To illustrate, consider (13).

- (13) Florence loves⁵ Bob. She wants to produce children. She does not sleep with Bob because Bob is married to Cindy. Instead, she waits till Cindy and Bob become divorced or she marries Gavin.

The scenario in (13) shows a conflict between Law B and Law A. Florence does not offend Cindy just to produce children with Bob. This is predicted by assigning Law A a greater strength than Law B. We also saw how the same universal laws manifest themselves in different ways depending on the situation in which the society finds itself (cf. the study of Situations I-IV above).

As an endnote to this section, I would like to mention that the universals given in Mohanan (1997), stated below, are probably relevant given what I have stated in (1).

⁴ We must distinguish between species that are biologically monogamous (e.g. seahorses, penguins, geese) with those that are not (e.g. lions) Those that are not biologically monogamous can still develop monogamous codes while intricately violating them (e.g. humans).

⁵ "Love" is not part of the theoretical framework, I am using it only for descriptive purposes.

- (19) Jinlian is Dalang's wife.
- a. Jinlian was found writing love letters to Ximen. They have never been on a date. Everyone in the village agreed they were adulterous (year was before 1911).⁶
 - b. Jinlian was found writing love letters to Ximen. They have never been on a date. Only when they were found holding hands did everyone in the village agree they were adulterous (before 1949).
 - c. Jinlian was found holding hands with Ximen. Only when they kissed did everyone in the village agree they were adulterous (before 1958).
 - d. Jinlian was found kissing Ximen. Only when they were found in bed did everyone in the village agree they were adulterous (today).

Scenarios (19a-d) show qualification of adultery scaled according to the degree of intimacy of the couple and parameterized by time. They can be accounted for with principles and parameters as in (20) and (21).

(20) Principle
Extreme intimacy with someone of the opposite sex is disallowed if that person is married to someone else.

- (21) Parameters
- a. Extreme intimacy prior to 1911 = writing love letters
 - b. Extreme intimacy prior to 1949 = holding hands
 - c. Extreme intimacy prior to 1958 = kissing
 - d. Extreme intimacy from 1958 = sleeping with each other.

Depending on the kinds of parameters involved, degree of intimacy or time period can be expressed as a scale. In our example above, a scale would capture the increase in intensity of intimacy reflected by the physical distance between the adulterous couple. This is a feat that (18a) cannot do. Nothing in (21a-d) is in conflict and no conflict resolution is necessary. Notice that (21) is very similar to the cognitive distance continuum given in (16).

I now move to (18b). Recall in section 2 the interaction between the Laws A-D and the situations I-IV. Given a formalism for conflict resolution, the same set of laws can yield different societies (polyandry, polygyny, or monogamy) with very little difference in ethical values. In a polygynous society, for example, even Bob's fifty-sixth concubine would be labeled adulterous if she copulated with Eric. In all the situations discussed in section 2, Laws A-D are available though some may be violated under specific circumstances. For example, if the husband is never at home, it would not be too surprising that his wife should love her neighbor. People generally do not want to violate any of the ethical laws. Yet, the interaction of those same laws would yield apparently opposite kinds of societies, polyandry versus polygyny or polygamy versus monogamy. This is something that principles and parameters cannot capture. There is just no way to state a principle with a set of parameters that will yield opposite results. Hence, (18b) cannot be true either. Expressions of variability (at least in ethical systems) call for both conflict resolution and variable manifestation of single laws.

⁶ The years are made-up arbitrarily. Moral judgements do not shift very suddenly. I use these dates as milestones of political change that may impact on China's society. 1911 marks the end of Manchu dynasty. 1949 marks the rule of communism.

4. Two conceptions on the foundations of ethical laws

This section assesses the difference between two conceptions of (14) - (16) which are really statements relating to cognition.

(22) Conception I

(14) - (16) are universal axioms and with a few stipulations, one can calculate all the ethical prescriptions of a society or individual.

Conception II

(14) - (16) are fundamental *forces* that constrain the formulation of all ethical laws from which we can then calculate the ethical prescriptions of a society or an individual.

The two conceptions in (22) appear to align with different epistemological traditions that cannot be adequately addressed in this exercise. However, I will suggest that Conception II is probably more suitable for our study. To make explicit my assumptions of the relationship between (1), (14), (15), and (16) as well as the Laws A-D, I offer (23).

(23)

My model assumes that cognitive possibilities are motivated and constrained by biological and environmental factors. Our cognitive abilities in turn constrain and motivate the ethical laws that we have as a community or an individual. These laws would generate prescriptions such as “*You shall not commit adultery*” or choice of actions when they interact with one another under various circumstances. This is more consistent with Conception II.

Conception I and Conception II are not empirically equivalent. Essentially, in Conception I, one can postulate a law that is contradictory to (14) - (16) and give that law high strength assignment. In Conception II, this is not possible because any law that is postulated must be motivated and constrained by (14) - (16). Conception II is therefore more restrictive than Conception I. Consider the scenarios in (24).

- (24) In Village Unlikely,
- a. Zoe found Yvette in bed with Xavier. Zoe is unacquainted with the couple but she knows that Xavier is married to someone else. Zoe is very angry with Xavier. The village chief grants Zoe **fifty punches** on Xavier.
 - b. Zoe found Wilma in bed with Vince. Vince is Zoe's brother-in-law. Zoe is angry with Vince. The village chief grants Zoe **twenty punches** on Vince.
 - c. Zoe found Ula in bed with Teddy. Teddy is Zoe's husband. Zoe is extremely angry with Teddy. The village chief grants Zoe **two hundred punches** on Teddy.

In (24), we have a situation where (16) is not entirely obeyed. The ethical system of this hypothetical village would require a law to the effect of (25).

(25) Ethical system in Village Unlikely

Law 1: The parameter of anger over betrayal decreases along cognitive distance (16).

Law 2: Anger over betrayal is maximum when one does not know the person who is the victim of the betrayal.

Law 3: Law 2 >> Law 1

Law 2 is storable within Conception I but not within Conception II. This is because Law 2 cannot be motivated by (16), nor is its formulation constrained by (16). A theory of ethics built within Conception II would predict Village Unlikely as pathological and therefore does not exist. If such a community did exist, Conception II would have to be rejected. However, since there is no evidence of societies like Village Unlikely, Conception I is rejected because it over-generates.

5. Can morals survive a genetic catastrophe?

I now consider what would happen should a genetic mutation destroy the predisposition of humans to form societies. Assuming the mutation does not destroy our cognitive abilities (such as language, memory, abstraction), the mutation will have no effect on the architecture in (23). The destruction of predisposition to form societies would entail the unavailability of (16) with an impact on (15). I restate (15) and (16) below as (26) and (27).

(26) The selfishness principle (cf. (15))

The value of the life/happiness of X along the desirability parameter in (14) alternates between the two poles of COGNITIVE DISTANCE of X.

(27) Cognitive distance (cf. (16))

self (x) not self (x)
 ←.....→

In this case, one expects an absolutely selfish "society". Every individual mutant will make judgments (I do not know if they are ethical in this case) based on maximizing his/her own happiness and survival. There will probably be no institutions for moral education (e.g. churches) or moral judgment (e.g. legislation). However, given what I have said about ensuring the survival of one's genes in section 1, the mutant woman will still try to make a man or as many men as possible solely hers to ensure the survival of her child. The mutant man will still

try to copulate with as many women as possible to maximally pass on his genes, but will help provide for his mate and child only to the extent necessary to ensure the survival of his child.

We would predict that the mutant will still be outraged by acts of adultery⁷ if that individual is the victim. In (3i), mutant Ada will still be angry with Cindy when she saw Cindy in bed with Bob. However, Ada will not be able to get any alimony for divorcing Bob. In (3ii), Ada would still apologize to Cindy in accordance with Law D.

A lot of the mutants' behavior would appear similar to us (the non-mutants). Whatever you mean by ethical norms, one can most certainly say that the new mutated species will have behavioral norms. Whether such norms are ethical would be dependent on one's view of ethics.

6. Thinking about theoretical linguistics

The strategies involved in finding an appropriate framework as well as the appropriate laws for ethics (in this article, adultery) would apply to evaluating frameworks in theoretical linguistics. Similar calculi using law **prioritization** (such as Optimality Theory) or **strength assignment** or **principles and parameters** setting (Rizzi 1982) have been used or proposed in theoretical linguistics.

Sections 1-4 used and evaluated these calculi by generating relevant scenarios, and checking if those situations are attested. The conclusion found here is that any one of these strategies is insufficient. Conflict resolution as well as parameter setting are required to account for the variability in the manifestation of universal ethical laws. In addition, the ethical laws are motivated by other factors such as biology, environment, and cognition.

We can draw from the study of ethical laws some lessons for the study of linguistics. Firstly, one can use thought experiments (i.e. constructing scenarios) to check if prioritization, strength assignment, or principles and parameters are useful and sufficient. One can then find out if those scenarios are attested in any natural grammar. For example, before one becomes too confident about Optimality Theory, one should check for ganging up effects, law reversals, or other such scenarios.

Secondly, the study of ethical laws points us in the direction of looking for external motivation. Section 3 showed the need to distinguish ethical laws and principles that motivate the ethical laws. (1) and (14)-(16) are fundamental *forces* that motivate and constrain what kind of ethical laws would be attested in any community. If we looked beyond linguistics, into biology or any other fields of knowledge, we might find certain motivations and constraints that would account for why certain linguistic laws are never attested. For example, why is the following law not attested in any known language?

(28) Even-numbered syllables must contain only voiced segments.

The cognitive distance law (16) is not directly part of ethical theory. It could be part of behavioral psychological theory. By appealing to it as a motivation for ethical laws, one could explain why Village Unlikely (in section 4) does not exist. By appealing to evolutionary theory, (1) would also predict that there can be no ethical law that advocates the destruction of one's offspring. There may be tribes that practice children sacrifice, but it is always under the belief that it was necessary because otherwise the tribe would perish in the wrath of some god. No tribe would pay attention to any god that says 70% of all the children in the tribe must be sacrificed yearly. This impossibility is due to the constraint that (1) imposes on all possible ethical laws.

⁷ I am not sure if we can still call this adultery or if the concept is possible without societies.

To conclude, this exercise offers (i) an outside view for the formalisms relating to conflict resolution in linguistic theory; (ii) a rough study in capturing variability across different systems using universal laws in domains other than theoretical linguistics and; (iii) a petition to search for motivations external to one's chosen field of study.

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The paper is the result of a class assignment when I was a third-year undergraduate learning linguistics with KP Mohanan. The task was to examine the kinds of mathematics used in theoretical linguistics by applying it to studying something not linguistics. I had never tried to publish this paper even though I had a lot of fun writing it. Thanks to *FLaP FIRST*, I now get to share a bit of that fun.

I thank Alex Alsina, my syntax teacher in the mid 1990s, for reviewing this paper. A large proportion of what I know about syntax I owe to Alex. In preparation for publication, Xu Nuo, one of the journal editors, conveyed to me a list of typographical errors Alex patiently listed, instructing me to read the manuscript thoroughly for errors. In case the reader finds anything in Alex's published review that does not match with this paper, it is probably because of changes I made. I am chaffed to bits that Nuo is Alex's PhD student, and envy her the learning she experienced with such an amazing linguist and teacher as Alex.

All faults mine.

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**Comments for Wee's
"Variability in the Manifestation of Universal Laws"**

Alex Alsina
Pompeu Fabra University
alex.alsina@upf.edu

Lian-Hee Wee's article "Variability in the Manifestation of Universal Laws" is a thought-provoking paper on how general principles interact with each other to account for observable facts. This idea is applied to mostly hypothetical situations involving ethical issues, particularly how different social groups define adultery and react to situations in which adultery occurs. While I have little to say about the domain of ethics, the topic of general, perhaps universal, principles and how these principles interact with each other has been the object of much debate and various proposals in theoretical linguistics. The existence of patterns found recurrently in unrelated languages suggests that there are cross-linguistically very prevalent principles and it is very appealing to think of them as universal principles. But very often these principles are found with variable effects in different languages. So, the question arises how to account for these variable effects.

Optimality Theory (OT) is one of the frameworks that deal with constraint interaction in theoretical linguistics. The introduction of OT implied important changes in the way constraints or rules were formulated. In pre-OT frameworks, the standard assumption was that a representation was well-formed if and only if it satisfied all applicable constraints; if it violated just one constraint, it was ill-formed. Let us call this class of frameworks the Inviolable Constraint Framework (ICF). This required constraints to be formulated in ways that tended to be specific to each language. OT, in contrast, allowed constraints to be formulated in much more general ways, because the restrictions or limitations on the application of the constraints were achieved through constraint ranking. If constraints A and B are potentially conflicting, in the sense that there are contexts in which both can apply, the relative ranking of the two constraints determines which of the two constraints will apply in those contexts.

ICF posits language-specific constraints, whose statement is often complicated by the fact that it is necessary to avoid situations in which an unwanted violation of a constraint may arise. On the other hand, OT posits universal constraints, which are stated in a maximally simple way thanks to the fact that OT allows for situations in which constraints are violated.

Wee, in his theory of ethical behavior, does not take full advantage of his ideas about conflict resolution. He posits an ethical universal, his Law D, which (modernizing the language) is:

- (1) Law D: Do not waste your energy.

Waste is a value-charged concept. It entails use, but adds to the notion of use the idea that there is an insufficient positive or fruitful outcome associated with this use. But how do we know whether energy is being wasted as opposed to being used for a fruitful purpose? How do we decide in an objective way whether the outcome of a given event involving the use of energy is positive or fruitful or, on the other hand, is not? It seems to me that, in the absence of a precise definition of what would qualify as a positive or fruitful outcome of an event involving the use of energy, the decision as to whether an event of use of energy is a waste of energy or not is strictly subjective. For example, deciding whether building a doghouse for one's neighbor's dog qualifies as a waste of energy or not depends on whether one likes dogs or not, on whether one likes that particular dog or that particular neighbor, on whether one wants to be on that particular neighbor's good books, etc.

In the situation described by Wee, Law D is invoked for the first time in order to explain why a given male in an imaginary society would provide for a child that the male in question does not know whether it is his or not. The claim is that Law D is in conflict with Laws B and C, restated as follows:

- (2) Law B: produce children.
- (3) Law C: provide the best for your children.

Crucially, in a situation in which a male does not know whether a given child is his or not, by not providing for it he puts the child's life in danger, which means he risks violating both Laws B and C. Wee assigns Law D a greater strength (0.6) than either Law B (strength 0.4) or Law C (strength 0.5), which means that Law D has to be complied with rather than either Law B or Law C separately. But if complying with Law D implies violating both Laws B and C at the same time, then we have an illegal situation. The sum of the strengths of these two laws is greater than the strength of Law D, which means that, in order to provide for one's children and ensure their survival (complying with Laws B and C), one has to "waste" some energy (in violation of Law D).

At this point it should be clear that it is not necessary for the law to include the concept of "waste", which needs to be distinguished from the more neutral "use". Given the strengths assigned to laws, it is sufficient to state this law D as follows, replacing the statement in (1):

- (4) Law D: Do not use your energy.

With the strengths assigned to Law D and to Laws B and C, it follows that Law D will be violated and, therefore, energy will be used, just in case this use of energy is necessary to comply with the other two laws mentioned. Therefore, energy is never "wasted", as the only situation in which energy is used is when there is a purpose to it, that is, when it is necessary to satisfy Laws B and C. Thus, taking into account the constraints, or laws, with which a given constraint interacts or conflicts allows us to simplify the statement of those constraints, in this case, by eliminating a semantic distinction ("waste" vs. "profitable use") which would require stating the conditions for deciding which of the two terms of the distinction holds in each situation.

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**Response to Alsina's Comments for
"Variability in the Manifestation of Universal Laws"**

Lian-Hee Wee
Hong Kong Baptist University
lianhee@hkbu.edu.hk

Gasp! Alex Alsina is right! So, this response is about how his review triggered me to ponder beyond the scope of my paper into thinking about "variation" that may have a less direct relationship with universal laws. My heartiest thanks for his comments!

In phonology, variation comes in two flavors: principled and random. The first is usually accounted for by some rule (or constraint interaction) and is thus part of the grammar. I am thinking of cases like unaspirated and aspirated plosives in English (e.g. [p] and [p^h]). These are not meaningfully contrastive in English even though there is a rule for where aspirated forms appear, i.e. sole plosive onsets of syllables carrying main stress. This type can be captured by the interaction of universal laws. I do not know if this type of variation can be lumped together with what is usually called "alternation", such as the choice of [z] or [s] for the English plural. Alternations tend to be narrowly used for cases where the change may be between what is phonemic in the language.

Random variation in phonology is typified by "free variation". For instance, alveolar [t] and dental [t̪], which are not contrastive in English, can be articulated with free variation without other speakers noticing. However, a Malayalee speaker will notice because these two are contrastive in Malayalam. For the Cantonese speaker, [t] and [d] are not contrastive, although [t^h] and [t] are. To the Malay speaker, however, [t] and [d] are contrastive, but not [t^h] and [t]. The point of all these examples is that what are free variations within each language is a matter of which parameters are irrelevant. For Cantonese, [voice] is irrelevant but [aspiration] is. For Malay, it is the opposite of Cantonese, with [voice] being relevant, but not [aspiration]. English [dental] is not relevant for coronals, although it is for Malayalam. While the parameters may be said to be universally available, one wonders if there is universality in which parameters are retained as active in any given grammar. Another way of thinking about my query is this: Are there languages that have free variation between radically different segments, say [a] and [t]? If not, what are the constraints of free variation? I have no answer to this at the moment, although I may venture to guess that it has to do with how many parameters are involved. [±dental] will be just one feature difference between [t] and [t̪].

The (ir)relevance of certain parameters is not the only source of free variation. In prioritization and strength assignment, if two forces are unranked with respect to one another, free variation may also result. For example, consider the three-body problem where the choice to orbit one sun or the other is random if a planet is in a position where the forces pulling it from both suns are exactly the same. Despite its randomness, this kind of free variation falls within the domain of discussion in "variability in the manifestation of universal laws". I am reminded of Anttila (1995, and also Anttila & Cho 1998) where the probability of a dialect can be predicted simply by the convergence that different Optimality Theoretic ranking hierarchies have on certain outputs for given inputs. These works show that one can predict variation of linguistic expressions/forms found in a society (or E-language).

Stochastic models produce variation too, but I would consider that to be a looser version of strength assignment or prioritization. There may be other sources of free variation that I have not thought of, and welcome readers to share them with me.

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Cantonese Classifiers at the Syntax-Semantics Interface

Tommy Tsz-Ming Lee
City University of Hong Kong
tszmlee@cityu.edu.hk

Abstract

This study explores a finer classification of classifiers in Cantonese and argues that the syntactic distribution of classifiers correlates with their semantic contribution. Based on the semantic and syntactic properties of seven different types of classifiers, I argue that classifiers function as either Cl-restrictors, Cl-dividers or Cl-measurers. I suggest a syntax-semantics mapping of classifiers under a cartographic framework, where each class of classifiers heads a functional projection between the Numeral head and the NP.

Keywords: classifiers, Classifier Phrase, count-mass, cartography, Cantonese

1. Introduction

In Cantonese, classifiers are widely assumed to fall into two classes: *count-classifiers* and *mass-classifiers*. According to Cheng & Sybesma (1999:515), mass-classifiers are “the classifiers that create a unit of measure”, while count-classifiers are “the classifiers that simply name the unit of natural semantic partitioning (i.e., with built-in semantic partitioning)”.¹ Meanwhile, it is also clear that the choice of classifiers plays a role in the denotation of a nominal. As showcased in the Cantonese examples below in (1)-(7), the semantic contribution of classifiers goes beyond the count/mass distinction. Roughly speaking, the classifiers in (1)-(2) belong to count-classifiers, where those in (3)-(7) belong to mass-classifiers.

- (1) 一隻象棋
jat1 **zek3** zoeng6kei2 ↗ an entity
one CL chess
'one chessman'
- (2) 一副象棋
jat1 **fu3** zoeng6kei2 ↗ an entity
one CL chess
'one set of chess'
- (3) 一堆象棋
jat1 **deoi1** zoeng6kei2 ↗ a collection
one CL_{pile} chess
'one pile of chess(men)'

¹ Despite some terminology differences, similar definitions can be found in Matthews & Yip (2011:109) for Cantonese:

- (a) *measure or mensural classifiers*, which denote quantities of an item;
(b) *type or sortal classifiers*, which belong with the noun and classify it in terms of some intrinsic feature.

- (4) 一盒象棋
 jat1 **hap6** zoeng6kei2 ↗ a container
 one CL_{box} chess
 ‘one box of chess(men)’
- (5) 一鋪象棋
 jat1 **pou1** zoeng6kei2 ↗ an event
 one CL chess
 ‘one game of chess’
- (6) 一種象棋
 jat1 **zung2** zoeng6kei2 ↗ a kind
 one CL chess
 ‘one kind of chess’
- (7) 一磅象棋
 jat1 **bong6** zoeng6kei2 ↗ a measurement
 one CL_{pound} chess
 ‘one pound of chess(men)’

Drawing on these examples, this paper proposes a finer classification of classifiers in Cantonese. Based on the semantic and syntactic properties of these classifiers, I argue that classifiers function as either Cl-restrictors, Cl-dividers or Cl-measurers, summarized as Table 1.

Table 1 – The proposed classification of Cantonese classifiers and their functions

Types	Functions	Examples
Cl-restrictors	Disambiguation of the denotation of the NP	(1)-(2)
Cl-dividers	Individuation of the NP	(3)-(6)
Cl-measurers	Creation of a measurement for the NP	(7)

In particular, I suggest a syntax-semantics mapping of classifiers under a cartographic framework (Rizzi 1997, *et seq.*). The gist of the proposal is illustrated in (8), following the spirit of Sybesma (2007), Cheng (2009, 2012), and Cheng & Sybesma (2014), where each class of classifiers heads a functional projection between the Numeral head and the NP.

- (8) A proposed split ClassifierP

As a side note, I remain silent on the issue of whether and how classifiers contribute to the count/mass interpretation of the NP (see, for example, Chierchia 1998, Borer 2005; see also Cheng et al. 2008 and Cheng & Sybesma 2014 for an opposite view).

2. Two lines of study on classifiers

2.1. Diagnostic tests for count-classifiers and mass-classifiers

The distinction between count-classifiers and mass-classifiers is usually taken to be reflected on some grammatical constructions. In Mandarin, *de*-insertion test shows that *de* can be inserted after mass-classifiers, but not count-classifiers (Tai & Chao 1994; Cheng & Sybesma 1999; *inter alia*).

- (9) Mass-classifiers [Mandarin]
- a. 三磅 (的) 肉
 san bang (de) rou
 three CL_{pound} DE meat
 ‘three pounds of meat’
- b. 兩箱 (的) 書
 liang xiang (de) shu
 two CL_{box} DE book
 ‘two boxes of books’
- (10) Count-classifiers [Mandarin]
- a. 八頭 (*的) 牛
 ba tou (*de) niu
 eight CL DE cow
 ‘eight cows’
- b. 九根 (*的) 尾巴
 jiu gen (*de) weiba
 nine CL DE tail
 ‘nine tails’

Two remarks are in order. First, although the same largely applies to Cantonese (with *de* replaced by *ge3*), it is unclear how the count/mass distinction is related to the insertion of *de/ge3*. Generally, *ge3/de* are regarded as modifier markers, but there is no consensus on their precise status. Second, in Mandarin, Li (2013) reports a number of counter-examples.

- (11) 一口氣能吃四十個的包子
 yi-kouqi neng chi sishi-ge de baozi [Mandarin]
 one-breath can eat 40-CL DE bun
 ‘able to eat 40 buns in one breath’ (Li 2013:104)

However, the test seems to give more consistent results in Cantonese.

- (12) ??一口氣食到四十個嘅包 *The Cantonese Counterpart of (11)*
 jat1-hau2hei3 sik6-dou3 sei3sap6-go3 ge3 baau1
 one-breath eat-can 40-CL GE bun
 ‘able to eat 40 buns in one breath’

Another diagnostic concerns modifier insertion. A restricted class of adjectives, such as *da/daai6* ‘big’, *xiao/sai6* ‘small’ can be inserted between the numeral and mass-classifiers, but not count-classifiers (Cheng & Sybesma 1999).

- (13) Mass-classifier [Mandarin]
 a. 一大張紙
 yi da zhang zhi
 one big CL_{sheet} paper
 ‘one large sheet of paper’
 b. 那一小箱書
 na yi xiao xiang shu
 that one small CL_{box} book
 ‘that one small box of books’
- (14) Count-classifier [Mandarin]
 a. *一大隻狗
 *yi da zhi gou
 one big CL dog
 ‘one big dog’
 b. *一大位老師
 *yi da wei laoshi
 one big CL teacher
 ‘one big teacher’

Again, Li (2013) reports some counter-examples as in (15).

- (15) 可以同時蒸三大隻豬
 Keyi tongshi zheng san-da-zhi zhu [Mandarin]
 can simultaneously steam three-big-CL pig
 ‘(It) can steam three big pigs simultaneously.’

In addition, in Cantonese, *zoengl* ‘sheet’ (*zhang* in (13a)) is regarded as a count-classifier in Matthews & Yip (2011). Also, *zhang/zoengl* ‘sheet’ seems to name the unit of natural semantic partitioning, instead of creating a unit of measure. Also, Lu (1987) suggests that the adjectives inserted between the numeral and the classifier always have a flavor of exaggeration. It is then unclear why the count/mass-distinction in classifiers should be sensitive to the flavor of exaggeration. We will return to the discussion of these two tests in section 5.

2.2 Classifiers realized as two functional projections

The distribution of classifiers in Mandarin and Cantonese is not identical. It is well-known that Mandarin bare noun can give a definite reading, whereas the Cantonese nouns must take a classifier to do so (i.e. a Cl-NP sequence). This indicates that Cantonese classifiers are crucial in establishing definiteness.

- (16) a. 書
shu [Mandarin]
book ‘the book’
- b. *(本)書
*(bun2) syu1 [Cantonese]
CL book ‘the book’
- (17) a. 那書
na shu [Mandarin]
that book ‘that book’
- b. 嗰*(本)書
go2 *(bun2) syu1 [Cantonese]
that CL book ‘that book’

Building on these observations (and some others), Sybesma (2007:241) suggests that while Mandarin classifiers primarily facilitate counting, Cantonese classifiers are unit-markers, which mark individuality or unit-hood of an NP, turning a semantically countable NP into a syntactically countable NP. In other words, “in Mandarin, the classifier is only there for counting, while in Cantonese we need it for individual reference” (Cheng & Sybesma 2014:259). This idea is implemented by positing two functional projections for classifiers (Cheng 2009, 2012). In Cantonese, Cl-U is designated for unit-marking, which is the base position for count-classifier; whereas Cl-C is designated for counting, which is the base position for mass-classifier.

- (18) Sybesma’s (2007) split ClassifierP

3. The semantic contribution of classifiers

This section illustrates how the proposed three classes of classifiers differ in their semantic contribution. Note that Zhang (2007) discusses the stylistic effects of the choice of classifiers, which is observed across the classifier types proposed here. Such effects seem to be related to conventional implicatures which I will set aside in this paper.

3.1 Disambiguation of NP—Cl-restrictor

This class includes (1)-(2), repeated below:

- (19) 一隻象棋
jat1 zek3 zoeng6kei2 → an entity
one CL chess
‘one chessman’

- (20) 一副象棋
 jat1 fu3 zoeng6kei2 ↗ an entity
 one CL chess
 ‘one set of chess’

This class corresponds to the so-called count-classifiers which “name the unit of natural semantic partitioning” (Cheng & Sybesma 1999:515). They must agree with the built-in semantic partitioning of the NP. In addition to its ‘naming’ function, they also *disambiguate* or *qualify* the denotation of the NPs, “by eliminating other possible interpretations in a richly encoded but under-specified lexicon” (Huang & Ahrens 2003:360).² They bear a close relation with the NP.

For example, the denotation of *zoeng6kei2* ‘chess’ is ambiguous in the sense that it can refer to a chessman or the minimal game unit. Classifiers of this type pick out a particular meaning and suppresses the other. As such in (19) and (20), although both of them refer to some entities denoted by the NP ‘chess’, the former refers to ‘one chessman’, whereas the latter ‘one set of chess’. The classifiers further qualify the denotation of the NP in the same domain (i.e. entities). Apart from (19) and (20), some more examples are given in (21)-(22).

- (21) a. 九十九朵花
 gau3sap6gau3 do2 faa1
 99 CL flower
 ‘99 flowers’
- b. 九十九棵花
 gau3sap6gau3 po1 faa1
 99 CL flower
 ‘99 flower plants’
- (22) a. 三本小說
 saam1 bun2 siu2syut3
 three CL novel
 ‘three novels’ ↗ ‘three books’
- b. 三部小說
 saam1 bou6 siu2syut3
 three CL novel
 ‘three novels’ ↗ ‘three stories’

As reflected in the translation, the denotations in (a) are substantially different from those in (b). While (21a) may be a welcoming gift on Valentine’s Day, (21b) can hardly be an appropriate one under the same circumstance. Similarly, (22a) focuses on the form of a novel as a book, while (22b) focuses on the content of the novels.³

In the absence of a classifier, it is unsurprising that the denotation of the NP can be ambiguous. (23) can mean the speaker lost a chessman or the game unit.

² Similar ideas can be found in Zhang (2007:51), who suggests “a noun entity may have shifting and different semantic references, and it is often through the use of a particular classifier that the meaning becomes clear and specified” and also in Adams (1986:242), who proposes that “the noun as a symbol is imprecise and its physical referents can have different enough characteristics that different classifiers are appropriate for them.”

³ See also Zhang (2007) for more examples in Mandarin.

- (23) 我嘅象棋唔見咗
 ngo5-ge3 zoeng6kei2 m4-gin3-zo2
 my chess lost
 ‘My chess(man) lost.’

3.2 Individuation of NP—CI-divider

This class includes (3)-(6), repeated as (24)-(27) below.

- (24) 一堆象棋
 jat1 **deoi1** zoeng6kei2 ↗ a collection
 one CL_{pile} chess
 ‘one pile of chess(men)’
- (25) 一盒象棋
 jat1 **hap6** zoeng6kei2 ↗ a container
 one CL_{box} chess
 ‘one box of chess(men)’
- (26) 一鋪象棋
 jat1 **pou1** zoeng6kei2 ↗ an event
 one CL chess
 ‘one game of chess’
- (27) 一種象棋
 jat1 **zung2** zoeng6kei2 ↗ a kind
 one CL chess
 ‘one kind of chess’

The characteristic of this class is that it *individuates* or *divides* the NP into a countable unit. It offers semantic partitioning, but it does not disambiguate the denotation of the NPs (unlike CI-restrictors). They do not have a direct relation with the NP. On a closer look, these classifiers can be grouped into different subclasses. The individuation function can be materialized in different domains. In particular, the output of individuation can be realized as entities, events and kinds.

3.2.1 Collective classifiers: (24) & (25)

The classifiers in (24) and (25) individuate the NP in terms of entities. In other words, (24) and (25) are forced to have an entity reading (as opposed to an event reading or a kind reading, to which we will return shortly). Matthews and Yip (2011) suggest two separate classes, namely, collective classifiers and container classifiers, corresponding to (24) and (25). However, the difference between these two classes does not seem to be reflected in the syntax. I group them into one.

Note that while *zoeng6kei2* ‘chess’ comes with built-in semantic partitioning (i.e. it is a count noun, given their compatibility with CI-restrictor), the semantic partitioning offered by CI-divider overwrites or ignores the previous one.⁴ Although both (24) and (25) denote some

⁴ It should be noted that individuation is not exclusively encoded at this level. Nouns can come with inherent individuation. But explicit syntactic means to realize individuation enjoys a higher status (and hence overwriting).

group of chess(men), they do not indicate the chess(men) are in separation or in a set (i.e. (24) and (25) can be ambiguous). Since multiple classifiers are disallowed in general, to disambiguate the two readings, the classifiers may form a modifier phrase, in the form of ‘one-CL-CL’.

(28) 一堆 [一隻隻嘅] 象棋
 jat1 deoi1 [jat1 zek3 zek3 ge3] zoeng6kei2
 one CL_{pile} [one CL CL GE] chess
 ‘one pile of chessmen’

(29) 一盒 [一副副嘅] 象棋
 jat1 hap6 [jat1 fu3 fu3 ge3] zoeng6kei2
 one CL_{pile} [one CL CL GE] chess
 ‘one box of sets of chess’

3.2.2 Event classifiers: (26)⁵

On a more abstract level, individuation can force an event reading. The classifier *pou1* in (26) individuates the NP and returns to an event object (Huang & Ahrens 2003). The event status of the resulting nominal manifests in at least three ways.

First, an event nominal can establish a temporal relation with a temporal subordinator (e.g. *zi1hau6* ‘after’). In (30), only the event classifier *pou1* is appropriate. It behaves like a VP which presumably represents an event, as in (31).

(30) 三 {鋪 / *種 / *副} 象棋之後, 大家都好劫
 saam1- {pou1 / *zong2 / *fu3} zoeng6kei2 zi1hau6, daai6gaa1 dou1 hou2 gui6
 three- CL_{event} CL_{kind} CL chess after everyone all very tired
 ‘After three {games / kinds / sets} of chess, everyone is tired.’

(31) 玩完象棋之後, 大家都好劫
 [vp waan2-jyun4 zoeng6kei2] zi1hau6, daai6gaa1 dou1 hou2 gui6
 play-finish chess after everyone all very tired
 ‘After playing chess, everyone is tired.’

Second, the ‘possessor’ of the event nominal is interpreted as an argument of the NP. (32a) suggests that the game is played by (probably two) teenage chess players (i.e., agents). (32b) and (32c) substantially differ from this respect in that the possessor indicates possession instead.

(32) 青年棋手嘅一 {a. 鋪 / b. 種 / c. 副} 象棋
 cing1nin4 kei4sau2 ge3 jat1- {a. pou1 / b. zung2 / c. fu3 } zoeng6kei2
 teenage chess player GE one- CL_{event} CL_{kind} CL chess
 a. ‘a game of chess played between teenage chess players’
 b. ‘a kind of chess that is known/ spread among teenage chess players’
 c. ‘a set of chess that is owned by the chess players’

Lastly, the event nominals are compatible with a subclass of verbs like *zeon3hang4* ‘proceed’ and *hoi1ci2* ‘begin’. Other types of classifiers are not possible in the same position.

⁵ The discussions here modelled after Huang & Ahrens (2003).

- (33) {a. 鋪 / b. *種 / c. *副} 象棋進行咗三個鐘
 {a. pou1 / b. *zung2 / c. *fu3} zoeng6kei2 zeon3hang4-zo2 saam1-go3-zung1
 CL_{event} CL_{kind} CL chess went on three-hour
 ‘The {game / kind / set} of chess went on for three hours.’

3.2.3 Kind classifiers: (27)

In addition to entity and event reading, individuation is also available in the kind domain. The less discussed kind classifiers such as *zung2* in (27), “explicitly mark that the nominal element that it selects and gives it a kind reading” (Huang & Ahrens 2003:361). It refers to the kind represented by the NP, instead of the entity (or the event). The kind status of (27) can be seen in the following ways.

First, since bare nouns in Cantonese can be used to give a generic reading, it is expected that replacing the bare noun with NP with kind classifiers does not alter the meaning. With the presence of kind classifiers (but not count-classifiers or event classifiers), (35) can be used as a paraphrase of (34) (given relevant contextual information).

- (34) 中國象棋好玩過國際象棋
 zung1gwok3-zoeng6kei2 hou2waan2 gwo3 gwok3zai3-zoeng6kei2
 Chinese-chess interesting than Western-chess
 ‘Chinese chess is more interesting than Western chess.’

- (35) 呢 {種 / *鋪 / *副} 象棋好玩過嗰 {種 / *鋪 / *副} 象棋
 ni1 {zung2 / *pou1 / *fu3} zoeng6kei2 hou2waan2 gwo3 go2 {zung2 / *pou1 / *fu3} zoeng6kei2
 this {CL_{kind} / CL_{event} / CL} chess interesting than that {CL_{kind} / CL_{event} / CL} chess
 ‘This {kind / game / set} chess is more interesting than that {kind / game / set} chess.’

Second, because of their kind-denoting character, kind classifiers are the only possible candidates in multiple-classifier construction discussed in Liao & Wang (2011). Under their analysis, (36) and (37) are argued to be partitive construction, where only kind classifiers can appear in the second classifier position. The whole object NP denotes some member(s) of the kind represented by the embedded NP.

- (36) 我有五副呢種象棋
 ngo5 jau5 m5-fu3 ni1 **zung2** zoeng6kei2
 I have five-CL this CL_{kind} chess
 ‘I have five sets of chess of this kind.’
- (37) 我見過五個呢停人
 ngo5 gin3gwo3 m5-go3 ni1 **ting2** jan4
 I met five-CL this CL_{kind} person
 ‘I met five people of this sort.’

3.3 Measurement—Cl-measurer

This class includes (7), repeated as (38) below.

- (38) 一磅象棋
 jat1 **bong6** zoeng6kei2 ↗ a measurement
 one CL_{pound} chess
 ‘one pound of chess(men)’

It creates the measure unit for counting without actual dividing. Importantly, it has a close relation with number, i.e., it must be used with numerals. Similar to Cl-divider, it does not disambiguate the denotation of the NPs. (38) only denotes some quantity (in pounds) of chessmen. They do not indicate the chessmen are in separation or in a set, or in any division.

Their close relation with numerals can be illustrated in the following two tests. The first one concerns classifier reduplication, which gives universal quantification over the following NP (Cheng 2012, i.a.). Reduplication of Cl-measurer is degraded, but not for other classifiers, as shown in (39). The marginality of (39a) can be explained by the absence of numerals. The presence of numerals is not required by other classifiers. (39b) and (39c) are fine.

- (39) Context: There is a quantity of chess that weighs three pounds.
 {a. ??磅磅 / b. 隻隻 / c. 盒盒} 象棋都好乾淨
 {a. ??bong6-bong6 / b. zek3-zek3 / c. hap6-hap6} zoeng6kei2 dou1 hou2 gon1zing6
 CL_{pound}-CL_{pound} / CL-CL / CL box-CL_{box} chess all very clean
 ‘{Every pound of / every / every box of} chess is very clean.’

A similar point can be made in (40a). It should be noted that universal quantification over NP with Cl-measurers is possible, as in (40b). (40b) is fine due to the presence of the numeral *jat1* ‘one’.

- (40) Context: There is a quantity of cloth that is three feet long. (Cheng 2012)
 {a. ??呎呎 / b. 每一呎} 布都好乾淨
 {a. ??cek3-cek3 / b. mui5-jat1-cek3} bou3 dou1 hou2 gon1zing6
 CL_{foot}-CL_{foot} every-one-CL_{foot} cloth all very clean
 ‘Every foot of cloth is very clean.’

Second, while the sequence of Cl-NP can give a definite reading in Cantonese, Cl-measurers can hardly be used in this way. The marginality of (41a) and (42) can be attributed to the absence of numerals.

- (41) {a. ??磅 / b. 隻 / c. 盒} 象棋唔見咗
 {a. ??bong6 / b. zek3 / c. hap6} zoeng6kei2 mou5-zo6
 CL_{pound} / CL / CL_{box} chess lost
 ‘{The pound of/the/the box of} chess is lost.’

- (42) *升水唔見咗 (Cheng & Sybesma 2014:260)
 *sing1 seoi2 mou5-zo6
 CL_{liter} water lost
 ‘The liter of water is lost.’

Although Cl-measurer and Cl-divider (especially collective classifiers) are usually

treated uniformly as mass-classifiers, there is reason to treat them separately in terms of their interpretation. While CI-divider gives an entity reading (as in 43a), its measurement reading can be forced by inserting *ge3* between the classifier and the NP (as in 43b). However, only (43a) is felicitous in the context of making order in a restaurant. On the other hand, CI-measurer consistently gives a measurement reading (with or without *ge3*), as in (43c) and (43d). Both expressions are infelicitous to make an order.

(43) *Context: Ordering wine in a restaurant*

- a. 三杯酒
 saam1 bui1 zau2 ↗ a container
 three CL_{cup} wine
- b. #三杯嘅酒
 #saam1 bui1 ge3 zau2 ↗ a measurement
 three CL_{cup} GE wine
- c. #三升酒
 #saam1 sing1 zau2 ↗ a measurement
 three CL_{liter} wine
- d. #三升嘅酒
 #saam1 sing1 ge3 zau2 ↗ a measurement
 three CL_{liter} GE wine

3.4 Interim summary

Based on the discussion, Table 2 summarizes the differences between the classification of classifiers in this work and other proposed classification.

Table 2 - The classification of classifiers in Chinese

Classification	Classifiers					
	CI-measurer	CI-divider			Event	CI-restrictor
Collective (entity)		Kind	Event			
This work [C]						
M&Y 2011 [C]		Measure classifiers			/	Sortal
	/	Collective	Container	Generic		
Cheng 2012 [C] & [M]		Mass-classifier				
	Non-divider	divider/ furniture	container	/	/	Count
H&A 2003 [M]		Measure classifiers		Kind	Event	Count
E.g.	(7)	(5)	(6)	(4)	(3)	(1)/(2)

Table 3 below adds two more columns to Table 1. The NP column and the Numeral column indicate the relation between a classifier and NP/Numeral. A plus sign suggests their close relation while a minus sign suggests the opposite. A logical possibility arises where a classifier interacts with both NP and Numeral (not shown in Table 3). We will return to this

possibility in the next section, where I suggest such possibility exists but is derived via syntactic movement.

Table 3 - Classification of Cantonese classifiers and their functions, updated

Classifiers	Functions	Examples	NP?	Numeral?
Cl-restrictors	Disambiguation of the denotation of the NP	(1)-(2)	+	-
Cl-dividers	Individuation of the NP	(3)-(6)	-	-
Cl-measurers	Creation of a measurement for the NP	(7)	-	+

4 Proposal

4.1 The three-layered Classifier Phrase

The proposal builds on the spirit of Sybesma (2007), Cheng (2009, 2012) and Cheng and Sybesma (2014), where the functional projection, Classifier Phrase, is split into two. Based on the classification and the corresponding semantic function listed in Table 3, I similarly suggest a split Classifier Phrase analysis, where each class of classifiers heads a functional projection between Numeral and NP, as in (44):

(44) The proposed split ClassifierP

The hierarchy of these classifier projections is determined by the relation of the classifier to the NP and the Numeral Phrase. As discussed in Section 3.1, Cl-restrictor has a close relation with NP, as it disambiguates or qualifies the denotation of the following NP. Also, it does not offer additional semantic partitioning but instead respects the one that is built-in in the NP. It stays close to the NP.

Cl-divider, on the other hand, does not bear any direct relation to NP. Indeed, it offers its own semantic partitioning and it may overwrite the one inherent in the NP. Also, it does not require the presence of Numeral Phrase and so it occupies the middle field in the split Classifier Phrase analysis.

Finally, we saw in Section 3.3 that Cl-measurer not only overwrites the inherent semantic partitioning of the NP, but also requires the presence of numerals. It is the only class of classifiers that display such requirement. It stays close to the Numeral head.

4.2 Movements in Classifier Phrase

Another half of the proposal concerns movement within the Classifier projection. Based on the base generation position for each class of classifiers in (44), I suggest that movement is also involved, by which classifiers originating from a lower position can acquire the function of a higher position. There are two types of movement.

First, Cl-restrictor can, and indeed must, move to Cl-divider. Cl-restrictor does not only disambiguate or qualify the NP, but they also necessarily individuate the NP (keeping the inherent semantic partitioning of the NP) at the same time. This movement is obligatory.

Second, classifiers in Cl-divider position (be it a base generated one or a derived one) optionally move to Cl-measurer for a measurement reading. The availability of this movement essentially allows all classifiers to acquire a measurement reading. It is then unsurprising that the examples in (1)-(7) can unproblematically fit into NP position in the measurement reading environment (i.e., a measurement reading is forced). Take as an example the Cl-restrictor *zek3* in (1). In (45), the sentence is forced to have a measurement reading because of the presence of *ping4gwan1* ‘on average’. (1) can fit into the NP position, despite the fact that it is a Cl-restrictor, which starts low in the structure. In particular, it first moves to the Cl-divider position for individuation (which is obligatory) and then further to the Cl-measurer position for measurement. In its resulted position, it bears a close relation with both NP and Numeral (hence [+NP, +Num]), which serves to fulfill the logical possibility suggested in Table 3.

- (45) 平均每個人有 [NP 一隻象棋]
 ping4gwan1 mui5-go3 jan4 jau5 [NP jat1 **zek3** zoeng6kei2]
 average every-CL person have one CL chessman
 ‘On average, everyone has a chessman.’

It should be noted that this movement is optional, since the NPs in (1)-(7) do not necessarily have a measurement reading. If there is no movement, no measurement reading is forced. For example, in (43a), the NP gives an entity reading.

5. Discussions

5.1 Back to the two diagnostic tests

While the *ge3*-insertion test works well in Cantonese (i.e. *ge3* cannot be inserted between NP and count-classifiers, see Section 2.1), it is unclear why the insertion should be sensitive to the types of classifiers. The current analysis offers a possible explanation for the observation. Assume that *ge3* also heads a functional projection and it is sandwiched between Cl-restrictor and Cl-divider. In the presence of *ge3*, the (obligatory) movement of Cl-restrictor to Cl-divider position is blocked, due to the Head Movement Constraint (Travis 1984), as illustrated in (46). On the other hand, *ge3* can be inserted between the non-count-classifiers and the NP because other types of classifiers can be base generated higher than *ge3*.

- (46) Movement with ClassifierP

Note also that the presence of *ge3* in Cantonese always forces a measurement reading. Under the current analysis, this amounts to say that Cl-divider movement to Cl-measurer is

forced if *ge3* is present. We then predict that Cl-divider, with the presence of *ge3*, cannot be used without a numeral (same as Cl-measurer). This prediction is borne out in (47) and (48).

- (47) *盒盒嘅象棋都好乾淨
 *hap6-hap6 ge3 zoeng6kei2 dou1 hou2 gon1zing6
 CL_{box}-CL_{box} GE chess all very clean
 ‘Every box of chess is very clean.’
- (48) *盒嘅象棋冇咗
 *hap6 ge3 zoeng6kei2 mou5-zo6
 CL_{box} GE chess lost
 ‘The box of chess is lost.’

Recall that the test does not work well in Mandarin. This can be accounted for by either (i) *de* is base generated below Cl-restrictor, or (ii) all classifiers in Mandarin are base generated as high as Cl-divider. The insertion of *de* is thus allowed, no matter the choice of classifiers.

As for the second test, which concerns modifier insertion, nothing in the current proposal prevents modification of the classifiers. This is a welcome result, since, as mentioned, the adjectives inserted between the numeral and the classifier always have a flavor of exaggeration (Lu 1987). Exaggeration concerns more about speaker’s intention than syntactic structure or semantic partitioning. It should be allowed across categories. Indeed, even for Cl-measurer, modifier can be inserted (*contra* Cheng 2012). In (49), while *bong6* ‘pound’ is an objective measurement, exaggeration is possible as long as the speaker views one pound as a huge amount.

- (49) 佢買咗一大磅肉返黎
 keoi5 maai5-zo2 jat1 **daai6** bong6 juk6 faan2-lai4
 s/he bought one big CL_{pound} meat back
 ‘S/he bought a whole pound of meat.’

5.2 Classifiers and polysemy

In (50)-(52), the same classifier may function rather differently, switching across classes. The current analysis would have to allow that some classifiers are polysemous. They are different lexical items with different base generation positions. No movement is involved.

- (50) *pun4* ‘plate’ (Cl-restrictor ↔ Cl-divider_{event})
 a. 呢盤棋有十隻
 ni1 pun4 kei2 jau5 sap6 zek3
 this CL_{plate} chess have ten CL
 ‘There are 10 (chessmen) on this plate.’
- b. 呢盤棋冇得救
 ni1 pun4 kei2 mou5 dak1 gau3
 this CL_{plate} chess not able save
 ‘There is no way to save this chess game.’

- (51) *faai3* ‘slice’ (Cl-restrictor ↔ Cl-divider_{collective})
- a. 一塊餅乾
 jat1 faai3 beng2gon1
 one CL biscuit
 ‘one biscuit’
- b. 一塊蛋糕
 jat1 faai3 daan2gou1
 one CL_{slice} cake
 ‘one slice of cake’
- (52) *cek3* ‘foot’ (Cl-divider ↔ Cl-measurer)
- a. 尺尺布都好闊
 cek3-cek3 bou3 dou1 hou2 fut3
 CL_{foot}-CL_{foot} cloth all very wide
 ‘Every foot of cloth is very wide.’
- b. ??尺尺布都好乾淨 (=39)
 ??cek3-cek3 bou3 dou1 gam3 gon1zing6
 CL_{foot}-CL_{foot} cloth all very clean
 ‘Every foot of cloth is very clean.’

6. Conclusions

This paper sketched a novel classification of Cantonese classifiers based on both their semantic contribution and the syntactic relation with numerals and nouns. In particular, classifiers serve as either restrictors, dividers, or measurers. Based on this classification, this paper maintained that the syntactic distribution of classifiers correlates with their semantic contribution and proposed a split classifier phrase analysis by suggesting that classifiers are realized in three different functional heads between the numeral head and the NP. The three classes of classifiers correspond to the three syntactic projections of classifier phrase (i.e. they have different base generation position). In addition, classifiers may obtain additional semantic function by movement. The analysis offers a potential explanation to the widely adopted *de*-insertion test in differentiating count-classifiers and mass-classifiers in the literature. A certain degree of flexibility of the use of classifiers is also encoded in the proposal by the possibility that the same classifiers may indeed have more than one base generation position (which is regarded as polysemy). Remaining issues include the compatibility with Mandarin classifiers and also the asymmetry between the distribution of Cantonese and Mandarin classifiers, which will have to await future research.

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粵語量詞中的句法—語意介面研究

本研究探討粵語中量詞的分類，並主張量詞的句法分佈與其語義功能相互關聯。基於七種類型量詞的語義和句法特性，我認為量詞可分為「限定量詞」(CI-restrictors)、「分隔量詞」(CI-dividers) 以及「測量量詞」(CI-measurers)。我提出在句法製圖理論 (syntactic cartography) 中量詞的句法及其語義有明確對應關係，不同量詞雖處於數詞與名詞短語之間，但佔據不同的句法位置。

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**First Reviewer’s Comments for Lee’s
“Cantonese Classifiers at the Syntax-Semantics Interface”**

The main argument of the paper, which is the cartography of classifiers proposed, is presented without ambiguity. The cartography proposed entails a new method of categorizing classifiers. The cartography and method of categorizing classifiers proposed are well motivated: The traditional categorization of sortal/mensural classifiers fails to capture the syntactic differences between Cantonese sortal classifiers and the question of when the item *ge3* can be inserted within a nominal phrase, and the paper proposed a way to analyse the two issues. Furthermore, this method of categorization proposed can potentially be applied to analysing classifiers in other languages, e.g. Vietnamese and Nung (Tai), where some sortal classifiers appear to perform more of noun categorization, while other sortal classifiers perform roles associated with number.

The author has discussed the relevant literature on classifiers in Mandarin and Cantonese adequately, and I do not find any factual, logical or methodological errors, or incorrect citations.

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Second Reviewer's Comments for Lee's "Cantonese Classifiers at the Syntax-Semantics Interface"

1. Comments

The argument is free of ambiguity, presented coherently and all the stated assumptions are discussed.

2. Queries

I only have one curiosity question on how different types of classifiers obtain the definite and indefinite readings. For the current proposal, it concerns the closeness of the CI type and the NumberP, which is a syntactic reason.

In addition to this, it appears to me that whether the CI can obtain the meaning of definiteness (let's say through CI-to-D movement) is also driven by the context. See the following example and the contrast between Scenario 1 and 2.

In Scenario 1, each student would have a different zoom link from Abby, which gives rise to an indefinite reading for the bare CI-N 'tiu zoom link'. Meanwhile, in Scenario 2, there is only one zoom link and every student shares it. So, the bare CI-N 'tiu zoom link' is interpreted definite.

Scenario 1:

Abby sent a zoom link to every student in the class. Each student has access to a different link.

Scenario 2:

Abby sent the class zoom link to every student in the class. All students share the same zoom link (i.e. unique and specific zoom link).

(1) Abby 寄咗條 zoom link 俾每一個學生。

Scenario 1: 'Abby sent **a zoom** link to every student in the class.'

(indefinite: a random link; it's possible that each student gets a different link)

Scenario 2: 'Abby sent **the zoom** link to every student in the class.'

(definite: when both the speaker and the addressee know that which link Abby sent and that is the one and exactly one zoom link; specific indefinite: when only the speaker knows which specific zoom link Abby sent)

An additional note on this part is simply a supplementary information, it does not impose any harm to the current analysis.

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The Moraicity of Sonorant Geminate in Tamil

Srinivas S.

Rishi Valley School, India

srinivas_s_k@aol.com

Abstract

This paper proposes that sonorant geminates are moraic in Tamil. The proposal firstly explains the absence of long vowel-sonorant geminate sequences in the language. Sonorant geminates being moraic and long vowels (typically) bimoraic, the absence of such sequences follows from a requirement that syllables be maximally bimoraic. The proposal also explains the occurrence of (C)VS(onorant) monosyllables in the language (e.g. [pal] ‘tooth’, [eŋ] ‘number’), based on the morphologically supported assumption that the final sonorant in such cases is a geminate. With the short vowel and the geminate each being monomoraic, (C)VS monosyllables would be bimoraic and minimally well-formed words.

Keywords: moras, syllables, sonorants, geminates, Tamil

1. Introduction

When it comes to assigning moras to consonants, languages fall into four classes. In Sindhi, for example, post-nuclear consonants are moraic (Walker 1997). In Kwakwala, post-nuclear consonants are moraic if they are sonorants, but not if they are obstruents (Zec 1995). In Sinhala, geminates are moraic (Davis 2003). In Tamil, sonorant geminates are proposed to be moraic in this paper, following Srinivas (2016: 99), a combination of the Kwakwala and Sinhala cases. This paper presents more evidence in support of the proposal.

The proposal that sonorant geminates alone are moraic among consonants in Tamil explains two phonological facts pertaining to the language. Section 2 explains the absence of sonorant geminates after a long vowel (*V:S_{Gem}) as following from a requirement that demands syllables to be maximally bimoraic. Section 3 explains the occurrence of (C)VS(onorant) monosyllables in Tamil as satisfying a bimoraic minimal word requirement, following the further assumption that the final sonorant in such syllables is a geminate (e.g. [maŋ] ‘soil’). That assumption in turn is supported by the perceptible doubling of the sonorant before a vowel-initial suffix (e.g. [maŋ.ŋ-il] ‘soil-in’). Section 4 concludes the paper, with a summary of its main claims and also points to its limitations.

2. Absence of *V:S_{Gem}

Syllables in Tamil come in the following shapes. There are open syllables with short or long vowels, as shown by the underlined syllables in (1).

(1) Open syllables in Tamil

a. (C)V syllables

- i. a.ram ‘virtue’
- ii. ma.ɖam ‘religion’
- iii. ki.laj ‘branch’
- iv. ko.su ‘mosquito’

b. (C)V: syllables

- i. i:.ram ‘wetness’
- ii. ka:.val ‘protection’
- iii. mi:.saj ‘moustache’
- iv. ku:.raj ‘roof’¹

¹ A post-vocalic vocoid is transcribed as a glide /j/, rather than as /i/, in this paper following the discussion in Srinivas & Ganesh Kumar (2018).

There are syllables closed by an obstruent, as shown by the underlined syllables in (2). These include syllables closed by a heterorganic obstruent (2a, b); those closed by the first part of a geminate (2c, d); and those closed by a sonorant-obstruent cluster (2e, f).

(2) Syllables closed by obstruents

- | | |
|--------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| a. (C)VO | b. (C)V:O |
| i. <u>na</u> t.pi ‘friendship’ | i. <u>mi</u> :t.pi ‘recovery’ |
| ii. <u>muk</u> .ti ‘salvation’ | ii. <u>pra</u> :p.tam ‘destiny’ |
| iii. <u>sak</u> .ti ‘strength’ | iii. <u>a</u> :t.kal ‘men’ |
| c. (C)VO _{Gem} | d. (C)V:O _{Gem} |
| i. <u>a</u> t.taj ‘aunt’ | i. <u>va</u> :t.ti ‘duck’ |
| ii. <u>ka</u> p.pal ‘ship’ | ii. <u>e</u> :p.pam ‘belch’ |
| iii. <u>ti</u> t.tam ‘plan’ | iii. <u>po</u> :t.ti ‘competition’ |
| iv. <u>ko</u> k.ki ‘crane’ | iv. <u>sa</u> :k.ki ‘excuse’ |
| e. (C)VSO | f. (C)V:SO |
| i. <u>ar</u> .tam ‘meaning’ | i. <u>ti</u> :rp.pi ‘judgment’ |
| ii. <u>kar</u> .tar ‘Christ’ | ii. <u>va</u> :rk.kaj ‘life’ |

When it comes to syllables closed by sonorants, there are three types: syllables closed by a heterorganic sonorant (3a, b); those closed by a nasal which is homorganic with a following stop (3c, d); and syllables containing short vowels closed by the first part of a geminated sonorant (3e). Crucially, there are no long-vowelled syllables closed by (the first part of) a geminated sonorant.

(3) Syllables closed by sonorants

- | | |
|----------------------------------|--|
| a. (C)VS | b. (C)V:S |
| i. <u>pa</u> n.bi ‘trait’ | i. <u>ma</u> :n.bi ‘honourable’ |
| ii. <u>ka</u> .vi ‘education’ | ii. <u>ke</u> :l.vi ‘question’ |
| c. (C)VN _{HO} | d. (C)V:N _{HO} |
| i. <u>am</u> .bi ‘arrow’ | i. <u>sa</u> :m.bal ‘ashes’ |
| ii. <u>pa</u> n.d̪i ‘ball’ | ii. <u>sa</u> :n.d̪i ‘mortar’ |
| iii. <u>va</u> n.d̪i ‘beetle’ | iii. <u>pa</u> :n.d̪i ‘a hopping game’ |
| iv. <u>sa</u> n.gi ‘conch shell’ | iv. <u>a</u> :n.gi.lam ‘English’ |
| e. (C)VS _{Gem} | f. *(C)V:S _{Gem} |
| i. <u>am</u> .ma: ‘mother’ | |
| ii. <u>ki</u> n.nam ‘small cup’ | |
| iii. <u>pa</u> .li ‘lizard’ | |
| iv. <u>ve</u> l.lam ‘flood’ | |

If long vowels are bimoraic in Tamil, as in other languages, the syllable types represented in (1b), (2b, d, f) and (3b, d) are at least bimoraic, since all of them have a long vowel. This is shown in (4) where (and elsewhere) ‘μ’ stands for a ‘mora’ in keeping with usual practice.

(4) Syllables with V:

The question then is how to account for the absence of long-vowelled syllables closed by (the first part of) a sonorant geminate (3f), especially given the occurrence of long-vowelled syllables closed by other sonorants (3b, d); and the occurrence of long-vowelled syllables closed by an obstruent (2b, d), or a sonorant-obstruent cluster (2f).

The answer lies in the moraic status of consonants in Tamil. In this connection, this paper proposes that sonorant geminates are moraic in the language (following Srinivas 2016:99). Given this proposal, the absence of the syllable type (3f) in Tamil is simply explained in terms of a requirement that syllables in the language be maximally bimoraic. The syllable type (3f) is trimoraic because it has a long (bimoraic) vowel followed by a (moraic) sonorant geminate, as seen in (5). It is therefore disallowed in the language. A non-initial geminate is represented in (5) and is assumed to be heterosyllabic.²

(5) Syllables with VS_{Gem}

The other syllable types, namely (1b), (2b, d, f), and (3b, d) are allowed because they are bimoraic, as seen in (4), and respect the bimoraic syllable maximum in Tamil.

The proposal that sonorant geminates are moraic in Tamil, as well as its connection with the bimoraic syllable maximum, is also supported by a process of vowel epenthesis whereby commonly used monosyllabic nouns become disyllabic in the language (Vijayakrishnan 2007; cf. Srinivas 2016: 99). Crucially, when a monosyllabic noun has a short vowel followed by a sonorant, the sonorant appears geminated in the disyllabic variant, as seen in (6b). When it has a long vowel followed by a sonorant, however, the sonorant remains single in the disyllabic variant, as in (6a).

(6) Doublets in Tamil

a. $CVS \sim CV:S\dot{i}$	b. $CVS \sim CVS_{Gem}\dot{i}$
i. $te:l \sim te:l\dot{i}$ ‘scorpion’	i. $je\dot{l} \sim je\dot{l}\dot{i}$ ‘sesame’
ii. $va:l \sim va:l\dot{i}$ ‘tail’	ii. $pal \sim pal.\dot{l}\dot{i}$ ‘tooth’
iii. $ma:n \sim ma:n\dot{i}$ ‘deer’	iii. $pon \sim pon.\dot{n}\dot{i}$ ‘gold’
iv. $tu:\eta \sim tu:\eta\dot{i}$ ‘pillar’	iv. $ka\eta \sim ka\eta.\dot{\eta}\dot{i}$ ‘eye’

The difference in sonorant gemination observed between the two sets of disyllabic nouns has to do with the moraic content of the initial syllable of these nouns. More precisely, the initial syllable of the disyllabic nouns in (6b) is bimoraic because of a moraic short vowel followed by a moraic sonorant geminate, as shown in (7). On the other hand, the initial syllable of the disyllabic nouns in (6a) is bimoraic because of a long vowel (like in (4)). Gemination of the following sonorant would create a supra-maximal trimoraic initial syllable in the words in (6a) (but not in (6b)) and is therefore disallowed.

² While this assumption is supported by the orthography of Tamil and a language game called ‘Ka Language’ (Srinivas 2016: 4-5), the arguments in this paper will hold even if non-final geminates are assumed to belong entirely to the coda of a syllable. They cannot belong entirely to the onset of a syllable because Tamil places a single segment restriction on its onsets (Srinivas 2016: 65).

(7) A CVSGem*i* noun

The above discussion has assumed that the final sonorants in the monosyllabic nouns in (6) are single consonants which appear geminated after a short vowel, in the disyllabic forms in (6b). The next section, however, contends that the final sonorants in the short-vowelled monosyllabic nouns in (6b) are, in fact, geminates, which help satisfy a bimoraic word minimum in Tamil.

3. (C)VS monosyllables

Consider the following monosyllabic nouns in Tamil, some of which are repeated from (6b). All of them have a short vowel followed by a sonorant:

(8) (C)VS monosyllables

- | | | | |
|--------|----------|--------|---------|
| a. pal | 'tooth' | b. kal | 'stone' |
| c. jeɭ | 'sesame' | d. muɭ | 'thorn' |
| e. eŋ | 'number' | f. pon | 'gold' |
| g. kaŋ | 'eye' | h. puŋ | 'wound' |

The nouns in (8) may be considered bimoraic given one of two assumptions. The first assumption is that the final sonorant in these nouns is single and moraic only in monosyllables.³ Along with the moraic short vowel, the final sonorant would therefore make a monosyllabic noun bimoraic, as in (9). The 'μ' with the subscript 'm' highlights that the singleton final sonorant is moraic, only because it is in a monosyllable.

(9) Final sonorant (singleton)

The second assumption is that the final sonorant in the given nouns is a geminate, and following the proposal in this paper, moraic. Along with the moraic short vowel, it would therefore make a monosyllabic (C)VS noun bimoraic, as in (10) where the (non-subscripted) second mora highlights that the final sonorant is a geminate.

³ See Rosenthal & van der Hulst (1999) on contextually moraic post-nuclear consonants.

(10) Final sonorant (geminate)⁴

There is evidence from Tamil in fact to support this second assumption—that the final sonorants in the nouns in (8) are geminates. For example, word-final sonorants of the kind in (8) appear perceptibly geminated when they are followed by a vowel-initial suffix, as in (11):

(11) Sonorant gemination before V-suffix

- a. pa:l-il ‘in a tooth’
- b. ka:l-a:l ‘using a stone’
- c. je|.l-in ‘of sesame’
- d. mu|.l-in ‘of a thorn’
- e. po-n-n-in ‘of gold’
- f. puŋ.ŋ-il ‘in the wound’

If the final sonorants in (8) are underlying geminates, their perceptible gemination in (11) does not require any additional explanation.⁵ The final sonorants in the monosyllabic (C)VS nouns in (8) may therefore be viewed as geminates so that the (C)VS nouns actually have the shape (C)VS_{Gem}. These geminates are moraic as per the proposal made in this paper and, along with the moraic short vowel, make the monosyllables bimoraic and minimally well-formed.

4. Conclusion

In summary, this paper proposes that sonorant consonants are moraic in Tamil. This helps explain two phonological facts pertaining to the language. The first of these, the absence of sequences involving a long vowel and a sonorant geminate follows from the requirement that syllables be maximally bimoraic. The second, the occurrence of (C)VS monosyllables, is explained by the further assumption that the final sonorant in such cases is moraic, and along with the moraic short vowel, makes the monosyllables bimoraic. One limitation of this paper has to do with the implicit assumption that non-sonorant geminates and homorganic nasal-stop sequences are not moraic. This assumption requires phonetic verification. Whether final sonorants in (C)VS nouns, which have been argued to be geminates here, are longer than those in (C)V:S ones require phonetic confirmation as well.

⁴ A more fleshed-out version of the figure in (10) would have the sonorant /l/ associated with two skeletal slots (X or C), with the latter in turn linked to the second mora (cf. Srinivas 2016: 112). In the case of (9), /l/ would be associated with one skeletal slot, which would be linked to a mora.

⁵ An onset requirement for the suffixal syllable may be satisfied by the re-syllabification of the stem-final sonorant consonant in the nouns in (11): e.g. /pa:l+il/ → [pa:lil]. Sonorant gemination in these nouns cannot therefore be motivated by any onset requirement. Furthermore, re-syllabification makes possible a more preferred contact between the two syllables in the nouns in (11) in that it makes a vowel, which is more sonorous, contact a sonorant consonant, which is less sonorous. Gemination of sonorants on the other hand leads to an equal sonority contact between the two syllables, such a contact being less preferred according to the sonority-based version of the Syllable Contact Law (Davis 1998).

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Comments for Srinivas's "The Moraicity of Sonorant Geminate in Tamil"

T. Temsunungsang
English and Foreign Languages University
temsunungsang@efluniversity.ac.in

This is a very brief paper on the moraicity of sonorant geminates in Tamil. It is written clearly and is an important contribution to understanding Tamil phonology. I was surprised that there is not much literature on Tamil geminates!

1. Comments

As the proposal of sonorant geminates to be moraic is already made in Srinivas (2016), the fourth class should be clearly attributed to him. It can be added that this paper brings in more evidence to support Srinivas (2016).

2. Some queries

- a. While the absence of long vowels and sonorant geminates has been shown clearly, I understand that the examples are surface level representations. Hence, are underlying V:SGem sequences (trimoraic) possible? If yes, what happens to such sequences on the surface? If it becomes bimoraic by shortening the vowel, this could be strong evidence for sonorant geminates being moraic.
- b. By your arguments in section 2, the sonorant coda in all CVS monosyllabic Tamil words are geminates. So, there are no CVS monosyllabic words in Tamil where the sonorant is a singleton? I raise this issue as I believe geminate structures are more marked than singletons, resulting in Tamil preferring a marked structure.

3. Relevant study

I recently read this article, which may be useful:

Ramprashanth Venkatakrishnan & Somdev Kar (2025) Sonorant Gemination in Old Tamil. *Bhasha*, vol. 4.1:95-121. E-ISSN 2785 5953.

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Response to Temsunungsang’s Comments for “The Moraicity of Sonorant Geminate in Tamil”

Srinivas S.
Rishi Valley School, India
srinivas_s_k@aol.com

I am grateful to the reviewer for their time and comments. They have raised two important questions, and these are answered below.

1. Underlying long vowel-geminate sequences

The reviewer points out that the absence of long vowel-sonorant geminate sequences is true of surface representations in Tamil. Their follow-up query is if there are long vowel-sonorant geminate sequences at the underlying level in Tamil, and if there are, what happens to them. While I am unable to think of such underlying sequences in native Tamil, evidence from the transliteration of English words in Tamil (Srinivas & Ramesh 2021) also seems to support the ban on long vowel-sonorant geminate sequences.

To illustrate the point, let us consider some words in English which have doubled consonant letters after orthographic ‘i’ (phonologically short /ɪ/ in the instances at hand) or orthographic ‘u’ (phonologically short /ʌ/), and those which have a doubled consonant after the vowel ‘a’ (phonological short /æ/). Crucially, the former vowels are written as short in Tamil as well, and the doubled consonant following it is reproduced as such, as seen in (i). The latter vowel, however, is interpreted as long /e:/ or /a:/ in Tamil, and because the vowel is long, the following doubled consonant is written as a single consonant in the Tamil orthography (ii), which mirrors its phonology.¹

(i) Short vowel-geminate sequences: English-to-Tamil transliteration

<u>E. phon. form</u>	<u>E. spelling/gloss</u>	<u>T. phon. form/orthography</u>
dʒɪ.mi	‘Jimmy (a name)’	ḍʒɪ[m.mi]i
mʌ.mi	‘mummy’	ma[m.mi]i
ɪ.nɪŋs	‘innings’	ɪ[n.n]ɪŋgs
dʌ.mi	‘dummy’	da[m.mi]i
dɪn.nə(r)	‘dinner’	dɪ[n.n]ar
sʌ.mə(r)	‘summer’	sʌ[m.m]ar

(ii) Long vowel-singleton sequences in Tamil transliteration

<u>E. phon. form</u>	<u>E. spelling/gloss</u>	<u>T. phon. form/orthography</u>
spæ.nə(r)	‘spanner’	spa:.[n]ar / spe:.[n]ar
scæ.nə(r)	‘scanner’	ske:.[n]ar
bæ.nə(r)	‘banner’	be:.[n]ar
tæ.nə(r)	‘tanner’	ta:.[n]ar
skæ.mə(r)	‘scammer’	ske:[m]ar / ska:.[m]ar

¹ In the Tamil writing system, V and CV sequences are written as single letters, whereas post-vowel consonants are written as separate letters.

Now, if the level of representation² where the relevant phonological cues (i.e. vowel quality) and orthographic cues (i.e. consonant-doubling)³ from English are adapted to Tamil is considered the input for Tamil transliteration, then the forms in (ii) have a long vowel-sonorant geminate sequence in the underlying representation, as seen under ‘Tamil UR’ in (iii).

(iii) Long vowel-singleton sequences in Tamil transliteration

<u>Tamil UR</u>	<u>Tamil SR</u>	<u>Gloss</u>
spa: <u>nnar</u> / spe: <u>nnar</u>	spa:.nar / spe:.nar	‘spanner’
ske: <u>nnar</u>	ske:.nar	‘scanner’
be: <u>nnar</u>	be:.nar	‘banner’
ta: <u>nnar</u>	ta:.nar	‘tanner’
ske: <u>mmar</u> / ska: <u>mmar</u>	ske:.mar / ska:.mar	‘scammer’

Such sequences being disallowed in Tamil phonology (and therefore orthography), the sonorant is de-geminated (instead of the vowel being shortened) in the surface representation, as seen in the Tamil SR. Following the proposal in the main paper (that sonorant geminates are moraic, see Srinivas 2026: 18), the absence of sonorant geminates after long vowels in transliteration may be straightforwardly explained in terms of a bimoraic syllable maximum.

2. CVS monosyllables with a singleton ‘S’

The reviewer also queries whether there are no CVS monosyllables in Tamil where the final sonorant is a singleton.

The implication of my analysis of CVS monosyllables as ending in a sonorant geminate is indeed that there are no CVS monosyllables ending in a singleton sonorant.

To my knowledge, the final sonorant in all CVS words appears perceptibly doubled whenever it is followed by any vowel-initial suffix. The comprehensive review of sonorant gemination in old Tamil by Venkatakrisnan & Kar (2025)⁴ confirms this. Since sonorant gemination before a vowel-initial suffix cannot be motivated by syllable contact or onset considerations (see note 5 in Srinivas 2026: 22), it is simpler to assume that the final geminate in CVS words is underlying, albeit it is marked compared to a final singleton, as pointed out by the reviewer.

Once again, I express my thanks to the reviewer for their comments and queries. These have led to the discussion presented here, which, I hope, the readers will find useful.

² Such a level presupposes a model of transliteration where the input from the transliterated language (in this case English) is subject to multiple scansions before they are rendered in the transliterating language (in this case Tamil). Upon this level, the phonological constraints of the transliterating language (in this case, Tamil) operate. The aforementioned presupposition has a precedent in Silverman’s (1992) proposal of multiple scansions for the adaptation of loanwords in a target language.

³ See Srinivas & Ramesh (2021) for a detailed discussion on how the transliteration of English words in Tamil is influenced by English phonology, English spelling and Tamil phonology.

⁴ I thank the reviewer for introducing me to this work.

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Tonality of the Zuoquan “Rù”

Kaixin Zhao

Hong Kong Baptist University

22482946@life.hkbu.edu.hk

Abstract

This paper establishes the tonality of Zuoquan Rù despite its lack of minimal pairs with other tones. Comparative analysis reveals that both the citation form and tone sandhi patterns of Rù differ from those of the other four tone categories (i.e. Yīn Píng, Yáng Píng, Shǎng, and Qù). Also, Rù patterns differently from the neutral tone in Zuoquan, which is demonstrably toneless. These observations indicate that Zuoquan Rù is a distinct tone category. Dialectological studies that rely on surface complementarity tend to suggest the Middle Chinese Rù as a syllable type rather than as a tone type. The case of Zuoquan cautions researchers against such sweeping generalizations that may mask deeper interfaces between syllable structures and tone types.

Keywords: tonality, tone category, Rù, Zuoquan, Middle Chinese

1. Rù: a tone category?

The Rù “entering” of Middle Chinese is considered by philologists as a tone category along with Píng, Shǎng and Qù (Tang 1958:20, Sagart 1999, Wang 2004:227), although phonology theorists have been inclined to understand it as indicative of a syllable structure closed by a plosive coda rather than as a tone (Cen 1942, Zong 1984, Zee 1991, Yip 1995:488f, Yang 1997). Data from modern Chinese dialects provide six possible modern situations of Rù in relation to the other categories, as shown in (1).

(1) Rù in different Chinese dialects (adapted from Tang 2022)

Situation	What Happens to the “Rù”	Syllable Structure
A-I	Middle Chinese Rù syllables/lexemes have been disseminated randomly across the other tone categories in modern Chinese dialects.	No plosive coda
A-II		With plosive coda
B-I	Middle Chinese Rù syllables/lexemes have assimilated systematically with another tone category in modern Chinese dialects.	No plosive coda
B-II		With plosive coda
C-I	Middle Chinese Rù syllables/lexemes remain distinct from other tone categories in modern Chinese dialects.	No plosive coda
C-II		With plosive coda

The situations in (1) are a combination of Rù’s assimilation to an extant tone category and syllable closure by a plosive coda. This paper provides an exploration of Zuoquan 左權, a dialect of the Jin sub-family spoken in Shanxi, arguing that it falls within the C-II category, hence providing evidence in favor of traditional philologists who consider Rù a distinct tone category.

2. Arguments against Rù as a tone category

Our understanding of Middle Chinese phonology stems from two sources: (i) historical

documents such as rhyme tables and (ii) reconstructions based on comparative studies of modern Chinese dialects, particularly through pronunciations of the Chinese character set that these dialects share. The reconstructions serve to provide approximate phonetic values of these characters that can then be cross-checked by the historical records, as instantiated in (2).

(2) Example of reconstruction using 東 “East” and 風 “Wind”

	Standard Chinese	Zuoquan (Wang 1991)	Cantonese (LSHK 2002)	Xiamen (Southern Min)	Middle Chinese (Dong 1993)
東	tɔŋ˥	tuəŋ˥	tɔŋ˥	tɔŋ˥ ¹	tuŋ
風	fəŋ˥	fəŋ˥	fɔŋ˥	hɔŋ˥	pjuŋ

From the pronunciation given in (2), 東 and 風 must have rhymed in Middle Chinese, and would belong to the same tone category. Less conclusive are their phonetic details, for instance, Beijing does not have the same vowel for both characters. This does not concern us here.² The prediction is corroborated by historical documents as in (3).

(3) A page from *Yunjing* (dating probably to 11th century, copy-edited by Zhang Linzhi circa 1160)

Image from public domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=1886756> with augmentation by Lian-Hee Wee (used with permission).

¹ The transcription refers to <https://www.zdic.net/zd/yy/my/%E4%B8%9C>. [tɔŋ˥] is the colloquial pronunciation of 東.

² There is some kind of vowel shift in Beijing from [ɔŋ] to [əŋ] when preceded by [+labial] onset. In traditional Beijing operatic arts, the [ɔŋ] is retained (<https://zh.wikiversity.org/zh-hk/老國音與京劇上口字對比>).

In (3), both 東 and 風 belong to the same row, indicated by the encircled head character 東. Items on the same row rhyme with this head character. These two characters belong to different columns, indicating differences in the places of articulation for the onsets. This part also corroborates the reconstruction where 東 begins with an alveolar consonant and 風 with a labial one.³

Of particular relevance to us is the bottom row 屋. This is the Rù category of characters. In some dialects, such as Beijing, the characters in this set have been randomly reassigned to the other categories, i.e. 東, 董, and 送, respectively the Píng, Shǎng, and Qù categories. The ancient philologists have not stated explicitly that these are “tones” in the sense that we understand them, i.e. modulations of pitch, or if they include other acoustic parameters such as syllable duration. One is only certain that the Middle Chinese philologists considered—justifiably or otherwise—Rù a separate category.

For purposes of dialectal investigations and historical reconstructions, it is indeed most convenient to consider Rù a separate category. However, since all the non-Rù syllables are not closed by plosives, there are no minimal pairs that contrast Rù tones with the other tones—a good reason to believe that Rù does not qualify as a phonological tone category (Xia 2003). The situation can be seen among many modern descriptions of Chinese dialects, which I illustrate here using Hong Kong Cantonese (hereafter, HKC). According to Middle Chinese tone categories and their respective divisions into the *Yīn* and *Yáng* registers, HKC has nine tones. Zee (1991) and LSHK (2002) explain that these nine tones can be reduced to six, graphically tabled in (4) as demonstrated in Cheung et al. (2024).

(4) HKC tone categories

Syllable Structure	<i>Shū</i> ‘spread’ (CVV; CVN)						<i>Cù</i> ‘hasty’ (CVQ ⁴)		
	Píng		Shǎng		Qù		Rù		
Middle Chinese	Yīn	Yáng	Yīn	Yáng	Yīn	Yáng	Yīn-1	Yīn-2	Yáng
Zee	[55] 1	[11] 1	[35] 1	[13] 1	[33] 1	[22] 1	[5]	[3]	[2]
LSHK	[53] 1	[11] 1	[35] 1	[13] 1	[33] 1	[22] 1			
	Tone1	Tone4	Tone2	Tone5	Tone3	Tone6			
e.g. /si/	‘silk’	‘time’	‘history’	‘city’	‘try’	‘matter’			
e.g. /sik/							‘color’		‘eat’
e.g. /sit/							‘reveal’		‘loose’

As can be seen in (4), the HKC Rù tones are short, correlating with the fact that syllables are closed, thus a group characteristically distinct from Píng, Shǎng, and Qù in terms of syllable structure. In other words, Rù tones are complementary to the other three categories. Furthermore, the three Rù tones have F₀ values similar to those of Yīn Píng, Yīn Qù, and Yáng Qù respectively. Thus, one cannot distinguish Rù tones on the grounds of F₀ profiles with respect to tones in other categories. The dashed arrows in (4) show how it may be more sensible to reclassify the Rù tones with other tones that have the same F₀ profiles. Hence, one does not need to recognize Rù as a tone category. Similar arguments have been made for other Chinese dialects (e.g. Huang’s (1960) treatment of Yangjiang, and Chen’s (2008) treatment of Hukou).

³ Assuming labiodentals are a subset of labials.

⁴ ‘Q’ represents plosives here.

If indeed all Chinese dialects allow the reclassification of Rù to the other tone categories, one could say that those who insist on Rù as a separate category had been illusioned by the CVQ syllable structure.

Evidence of complementarity in terms of syllable structure and similarity in F0 profiles is convincing only to a certain degree. A more important consideration that must be made pertains to phonological patterning. In Chinese dialects where tone sandhi may be observed, one must check the consistency in patterning of the Rù syllables with the identified tone category. Since HKC does not have much tone sandhi, it does not qualify as a strong case study on the identity of Rù. I now turn to the Zuoquan dialect for a more definitive argument.

3. Phonetic description of Zuoquan Rù

The Jin dialect Zuoquan is mainly spoken in the eastern part of Shanxi Province, China. Hou & Wen (1993:377) classify Zuoquan as belonging to the Yangquan area subgroup of Shanxi's Central district dialect. Like other Jin dialects, Zuoquan retains the Middle Chinese Rù category, in that these syllables are consistently closed by a glottal stop /ʔ/ (Wang:1991:5, although Hou & Wen 1993:7, 430 observe that the glottal stop may not be very evident). The Zuoquan tone inventory is provided in (5).

(5) Zuoquan tone inventory (cited from Wang 1991:5, Hou & Wen 1993:429-431)⁵

Middle Chinese Category	Píng		Shǎng ⁶	Qù	Rù
	Yīn	Yáng			
Zuoquan tone values	[53] ʔ	[21] ʔ	[53] ʔ	[35] ʔ	[2] ʔ

Prima facie, the F0 profile of Rù appears to be different from the other four tones. However, given Rù's shortness, one would be justified to query if there is indeed a meaningful difference between Yáng Píng [21] and Rù [2], or even more radically between Qù [35] and Rù [2].⁷ Zuoquan does not distinguish between more than three levels of pitch height, so there are grounds to doubt if [2] and [3] are meaningfully contrastive tone values. The glottal stop in Rù syllables may have masked the latter half of any tone contour, as illustrated in (6).

(6) Masking effect of obstruent plosives

In (6), we imagine a tone as being made up of tone features. Typically, onsets do not count for tone (Yip 2002:73; Wee 2019:chapter 3). This is evidently so since there are onsetless syllables that carry tone in many tone languages. Since tone is ostensibly pitch, the second half of a tone would be suppressed if it is associated with a voiceless segment (in grey box). Thus, if indeed Rù is the effect of a syllable having a VQ rhyme, and thus belongs to one of the other extant

⁵ Hou & Wen (1993) indicated that the Rù is short, but Wang (1991) was silent on the issue.

⁶ However, Wang (1991) observes that Yīn Píng and Shǎng are indistinguishable in monosyllabic words, but they have different tone sandhi patterns.

⁷ We shall see later an unexpected twist when Qù turns out to have two variants.

tone categories, what we must do is to compare the F0 profile of the Rù syllables proportionately with the F0 profiles of the syllable nucleus of the other tone categories.

3.1 Comparisons of Rù in citation with Yáng Píng and Qù

By citation, I refer to the tone properties of a Chinese syllable when uttered in isolation. Whether or not the citation tone is the underlying form would require further analysis, although the citation tone is often assumed to be identical to the underlying form. I make no such assumptions here.

To complement the documentation of Wang (1991) and Hou & Wen (1993), I look into pitch tracks from data of my own fieldwork.⁸ F0 extractions using Praat largely corroborate with Wang's and Hou & Wen's studies, although my investigations revealed Qù to have two different forms (more on this later). One therefore needs to compare Rù with Yáng Píng, and with Qù. Their citation F0 profiles are shown in (7).

(7) Citation F0 profiles of Rù, Yáng Píng, and Qù in actual time

a. Comparison of Rù with Yáng Píng

b. Comparison of Rù with Qù

⁸ Subject, 25 years old at time of data collection, speaks Zuoquan natively and uses the language at home. Sample size of data is about 246 monosyllabic words and 165 disyllabic words covering all Middle Chinese tone categories. Although my data set is small, it accords well with the published literature, hence validated.

Using Xu (2013)'s Praat script *ProsodyPro*, each F0 profile is constructed using the mean F0 values at 10% intervals for the duration of the syllable rhymes.⁹ Error bars provide the standard deviation around the time-normalized means with matching colors. The rhyme part of Rù syllables have a mean duration of ~141ms, Yáng Píng ~296ms, Qù-1 ~182ms, and Qù-2 ~242ms. The F0 profiles in (7) are scaled according to their time ratios.

In (7a), Rù and Yáng Píng have slight overlap within one standard deviation of their mean values. Their largest difference in the mean F0 values across the sampled points is less than 15Hz. This is smaller than a minor-second in musical terms, and can hardly be said to be meaningfully contrastive given the speaker's pitch ranges around 170-300 Hz. With respect to Zuoquan's tonal inventory, even Chao's (1930) very subtle five-way contrast in tone levels does not make such a fine distinction. Utilizing Shi's (1986) formula in (8a), the five tone levels of my Zuoquan speaker's pitch range are given in (8b).

(8) a. Shi's (1986) formula

$$T = \frac{\lg x - \lg b}{\lg a - \lg b} * 5$$

, where *a* and *b* are respectively the upper and lower limits of the speaker's pitch range; *T* refers to tone levels. By setting *T* as 1 to 4, *x* can be calculated to indicate the pitch value at each level's boundary.

b. Pitch ranges of my Zuoquan speaker in Chao's (1930) tone values

Chao's (1930) tone levels	Pitch Range (Hz)
5	266~297
4	239~266
3	214~239
2	192~214
1	172~192

Note that the tonal inventory of Zuoquan does not require five levels of distinctions in pitch height (cf. (5)). As such, (7a) suggests Rù to be possibly Yáng Píng in the guise of a CVQ syllable, but let us move forward to consider Qù in (7b).

As mentioned earlier, my field investigations revealed Qù to have two different citation forms, both presented in (7b) as purple lines. The convex profile Qù-2 on the top of the graph probably corresponds with Wang (1991) or Hou & Wen (1993), given its higher register and initial rising profile. The F0 profile Qù-1 was an unexpected discovery. Having two different Qù profiles may indicate (i) an emerging split of Qù into two tones, or (ii) the Middle Chinese Yīn and Yáng sub-categories. Since my focus is on Rù, I shall not speculate on these options that lie beyond the scope of this paper.

The F0 profile for Qù-2 is too far away to be a candidate for Rù. In comparison, Qù-1's profile is nearly identical to Rù. Considering both (7a) and (7b), Yáng Píng and Qù-1 are two possible categories for which one may classify Rù.

3.2 Comparisons in tone sandhi contexts

3.2.1 Rù when followed by another syllable

Zuoquan Rù undergoes tone sandhi when followed by Yīn Píng or Shǎng (i.e. both [53] ㄩˊ in

⁹ Where there are on-glides, these would only be included if the spectrograms indicate clear sonority, otherwise they are classified as part of the onset.

citation forms), as in (9a). For comparison, we consider also Rù when followed by other tones (i.e. tones whose citation forms are not [53]), as in (9b). Both are profiled in (10).

- (9) Patterns of Zuoquan Rù tone sandhi (see also Wang 1991:7f)
- a. Rù [2] → [4] / ___ {Yīn Píng; Shǎng}
 - i. 十 [ʃəʔ 4] + 三 Yīn Píng → 十三 [ʃəʔ 1 ɛ ʅ] ‘thirteen’
 - ii. 刻 [kʰəʔ 4] + 苦 Shǎng → 刻苦 [kʰəʔ 1 kʰu ʅ] ‘diligent’
 - b. Rù [2] → [2] / ___ {Yáng Píng, Qù or Rù}
 - i. 突 [tuəʔ 4] + 然 Yáng Píng → 突然 [tuəʔ 4 zɛ 4] ‘sudden’
 - ii. 失 [ʃəʔ 4] + 望 Qù → 失望 [ʃəʔ 4 vɔ 4] ‘disappoint’
 - iii. 職 [tʃəʔ 4] + 業 Rù → 職業 [tʃəʔ 4 ieʔ 4] ‘occupation’

(10) The citation and sandhi profiles of Rù

The F0 profiles in (10) offer a comparison for Rù in three different contexts: (10a) is Rù when followed by syllables that are either Yīn Píng or Shǎng; (10b) is Rù when followed by syllables that are either Yáng Píng, Qù or Rù; and (10c) is Rù in citation. The contours of (10b) and (10c) overlap in their standard deviation, but (10a) is a radical departure.

3.2.2 Comparison between Rù and Qù

Noteworthy in (10) is the fact that Rù has two different pitch forms depending on the tones of syllables that follow it. However, Qù (i.e. both Qù-1 and Qù-2) is always a rising tone when followed by another syllable, as exemplified in (11).

(11) The citation and sandhi profiles of Qù

Since Qù and Rù behave radically differently in sandhi contexts, any suggestion that Rù could be grouped with Qù is untenable.¹⁰

3.2.3 Comparison between Rù and Yáng Píng

Yáng Píng exhibits a sandhi pattern similar to that of Rù. Both become rising when followed by Yīn Píng or Shǎng, as shown in (12).

(12) Yáng Píng followed by another syllable (see also Wang 1991:6)

- a. Yáng Píng [21] → [35] / ___ {Yīn Píng; Shǎng}
- i. 神 [ʃəŋ ɿ] + 經 Yīn Píng → 神經 [ʃəŋ ɿ tɛiəŋ ɿ] ‘nerve’
 - ii. 寒 [xɛ ɿ] + 冷 Shǎng → 寒冷 [xɛ ɿ ləŋ ɿ] ‘cold’
- b. Yáng Píng [21] → [21] / ___ {Yáng Píng, Qù or Rù}
- i. 農 [nuəŋ ɿ] + 民 Yáng Píng → 農民 [nuəŋ ɿ miəŋ ɿ] ‘peasant’
 - ii. 毛 [mo ɿ] + 病 Qù → 毛病 [mo ɿ piəŋ ɿ] ‘illness’
 - iii. 顏 [ie ɿ] + 色 Rù → 顏色 [ie ɿ səʔ ɿ] ‘color’
- c. The citation and sandhi profiles of Yáng Píng

The F0 profiles of Yáng Píng in (12) are respectively comparable to those of Rù in (10). I

¹⁰ Recall (7) and accompanying discussion.

juxtapose them in (13) in a way that captures their durational differences.

(13) Comparisons of Rù and Yáng Píng when followed by other syllables

a. Rù and Yáng Píng before Yīn Píng or Shǎng

b. Rù and Yáng Píng before Yáng Píng, Qù or Rù

The overlap observed in (13b) that might qualify Rù and Yáng Píng as being the same tone. However, that is overturned by how the two profiles in (13a) have almost no overlapping sections. Lest, we are too hasty, let us entertain the possibility that Rù is not just the first half of the Yáng Píng tone, but rather the entire Yáng Píng conflated into the short duration of Rù. To check this possibility, one must time-normalize both Rù and Yáng Píng for comparison, as shown in (14).

(14) Time-normalized F0 profiles for Rù and Yáng Píng

a. Rù and Yáng Píng before Yīn Píng or Shǎng (cf. (13a))

b. Rù and Yáng Píng before Yáng Píng, Qù or Rù (cf. (13b))

c. In citation form (cf. (7a))

The above comparisons show that Rù and Yáng Píng generally share a similar profile in three different contexts respectively. However, there are some rather pronounced differences. In all cases, Rù's curvature is not as pronounced as Yáng Píng, and they do not overlap in many instances. Phonetically, there seems to be enough evidence to say that they are not the same.

Let me make one last effort for Yáng Píng and suggest that the reason behind the difference in (14) is the speaker's attempt at conflating the entire Yáng Píng into the short duration of Rù. Closed by the glottal stop, the speaker is compelled to compromise so that the F0 profile for Rù is not as pronounced as for Yáng Píng. Such compromise has been reported, for instance, in Shih's (2008) study on how increasing speeds flatten tone contours. If this is indeed the case, classifying Rù as Yáng Píng may still be potentially viable. The next section looks into this possibility.

4. Testing the conflation theory

If indeed the differences in F0 profiles between Yáng Píng and Rù in (14) may be attributed to the conflation of the entire tone contour into the shorter duration Rù closed syllable, then one would expect that when Yáng Píng is uttered in greater speed, the profiles would shift towards the Rù (hereafter R-shift). Conversely, when Rù syllables are uttered more slowly, they should exhibit F0 profiles similar to that of Yáng Píng (hereafter YP-shift).

In (15) below, I provide one such study on the effect of speed, with regard to the citation tones.

(15) Shifts in citation tones

Mean duration of the rhyme of Rù syllables is 141ms, and that of Yáng Píng is 296ms. In my collected data, the fastest Yáng Píng rhyme is 237ms from syllable 牛 [niʌŋ], and the slowest Rù rhyme is 174ms from syllable 别 [pieʔ].

In (15a), we see that faster Yáng Píng led to a flattening of the contour, but lowered the F0 profile away from Rù. This is contrary to the R-shift prediction. In (15b), slowing down Rù does produce a YP-shift.

When Rù and Yáng Píng come before Yīn Píng or Shǎng, they sandhi into a rising profile. These profiles would also be predicted for R- and YP-shifts, as shown in (16).

(16) Rù and Yáng Píng before Yīn Píng or Shǎng

When followed by Yīn Píng or Shǎng, the mean duration of rhyme of Rù syllables is 112ms, and that of Yáng Píng is 218ms. In my collected data, the fastest Yáng Píng rhyme in such sandhi contexts is 201ms from syllable 燃 [zɛ], and the slowest Rù rhyme is 146ms from syllable 發 [faʔ].

Here, the F0 of the fastest Yáng Píng in (16a) shifts towards the Rù, but its contour is still distinct from Rù. A similar pattern is observed for the slowest Rù in (16b). Thus, (16) does not support the R- and YP-shifts prediction.

To complete the comparisons, (17) presents the cases where Rù and Yáng Píng come before Yáng Píng, Qù or Rù.

(17) Rù and Yáng Píng come before Yáng Píng, Qù or Rù

When followed by Yáng Píng, Qù or Rù, the mean duration of rhyme of Rù syllables is 114ms, and that of Yáng Píng is 212ms. In my collected data, the fastest Yáng Píng rhyme in such sandhi contexts is 139ms from syllable 蝴 [xu], and the slowest Rù rhyme is 183ms from syllable 押 [iaʔ].

In (17a), the fastest Yáng Píng rhyme (at 139ms) comes close to the mean duration of the Rù rhyme (114ms). However, the effect observed is that it does not approximate Rù at all, hence not R-shifting. The shift in (17b) is also unlikely to be a case of YP-shift.

Throughout (15), (16), and (17), the R-shifts and the YP-shifts did not yield consistent results. This makes it difficult to defend a position for Rù to be classified as Yáng Píng. If they were indeed the same tone, then we should predict convergence in the shifts when articulation speed is changed. In fact, there is evidence that Rù is not a case of a conflated Yáng Píng, as in (18).

(18) A pronounced Rù F0 profile when articulated quickly (compare (16b))

In (18), we can see that the F0 profile of Rù is pronounced even at a very fast speed. This means that the difference between F0 profiles of Rù and Yáng Píng is not due to the short duration of Rù being a closed syllable.

5. Tonological status of Zuoquan Rù

The preceding paragraphs have argued that Zuoquan Rù cannot be classified as any of the other extant tone categories, despite the lack of minimal pairs due to Rù being a closed syllable. The new question that arises is if Rù itself is a tone category. To qualify, one must find evidence that Rù syllables carry underlying tones. Otherwise, it is possible that Rù syllables are toneless and hence do not form a tone category of their own. Fundamentally, the question boils down to whether Zuoquan has five tones or just four tones with the option of tonelessness. There is evidence that Zuoquan has toneless syllables, which I will demonstrate it is fundamentally

different from Rù.

Zuoquan has neutral tone syllables that can be shown to be toneless. Three main pieces of evidence are that Zuoquan neutral tone syllables are (i) indicative of morphosyntactic operations that lexicalize phrases or affixation (Wee 2022 for discussion), therefore unable to stand alone, (ii) do not trigger tone sandhi, and (iii) have a relatively unstable F0 profile.

That neutral tone syllables in Zuoquan cannot stand alone is easy to demonstrate. In words such as those in (19), the syllable with neutral tone is indicated with a subscript “0”.

- (19) a. Tone neutrality from lexicalization
- i. 東 [tuəŋ_{Yīn Píng}] ‘east’ + 西 [ɕi_{Yīn Píng}] ‘west’
 - ii. 東西 [tuəŋ_{Yīn Píng} - ɕi₀] ‘stuff, things’
 - iii. *ɕi₀
- b. Tone neutral suffix
- i. 俺 [ŋɛ Shǎng] ‘I’ + 們 [məŋ₀] ‘plural suffix’ → 俺們 [ŋɛ-məŋ₀] ‘we’
 - ii. *-məŋ₀
- c. Tone neutrality from partial reduplication
- i. 姐 [tɕi Shǎng] ‘older female sibling’
 - ii. 姐姐 [tɕi Shǎng - tɕi₀] ‘older sister’
 - iii. *tɕi₀

We can show that these neutral tone syllables in (19) are phonologically neutral in that they do not trigger tone sandhi in Zuoquan. A number of Zuoquan tone sandhi patterns presented earlier are repeated in (20) with two other sandhi rules that had not been discussed.

- (20) Tone sandhi in Zuoquan
- a. Qù → [high rising] / ___ {any tone} (cf. (11a))
 - b. Yáng Píng → [low rising] / ___ {Yīn Píng, Shǎng} (cf. (12ci))
 - c. Yīn Píng → [convex] / ___ {Yīn Píng, Shǎng}
 - d. Shǎng → [convex] / ___ Shǎng

Ignoring the details of the sandhi patterns which are tangential to this paper, notice that all tones, except neutral tones, are capable of triggering sandhi (e.g. (20a)). Syllables do not undergo sandhi at all when followed by neutral tones, as exemplified in (21).

- (21) a. With neutral tone from lexicalization
- i. 東西 tuəŋ_{Yīn Píng}-ɕi₀ ‘stuff, things’
 - ii. 眉毛 mæɛ_{Yáng Píng}-m₀ ‘eyebrow’
 - iii. 尾巴 i Shǎng-pa₀ ‘tail’
 - iv. 豆腐 tʌʃ_{Qù}-fu₀ ‘tofu’
 - v. 核桃 kəʔ_{Rù}-tʰ₀ ‘walnut’
- b. With tone neutral suffixation
- i. 丟啦 tiʌʃ_{Yīn Píng}-la₀ ‘have lost’
 - ii. 來啦 læɛ_{Yáng Píng}-la₀ ‘have come’
 - iii. 懂啦 tuəŋ_{Shǎng}-la₀ ‘have understood’
 - iv. 忘啦 vɔ_{Qù}-la₀ ‘have forgotten’
 - v. 吃啦 tʃʰəʔ_{Rù}-la₀ ‘have eaten’

- c. With neutral tone partial reduplication
- | | | | |
|------|----|--|------------------------|
| i. | 姑姑 | ku _{Yīn} Píng-ku ₀ | ‘paternal aunt’ |
| ii. | 爺爺 | i _{Yáng} Píng-í ₀ | ‘paternal grandfather’ |
| iii. | 姐姐 | tɕi _{Shāng} -tɕi ₀ | ‘older sister’ |
| iv. | 妹妹 | mæe _{Qù} -mæe ₀ | ‘younger sister’ |
| v. | 歇歇 | ɕieʔ _{Rù} -ɕieʔ ₀ | ‘take a break’ |

In (21), all the syllables preceding the neutral-toned syllable are uttered in citation form and do not undergo the sandhi processes listed in (20).

The F0 profiles of Zuoquan neutral tone syllables also indicate their phonologically toneless nature, as shown in (22).

(22) The pitch profile of neutral tone following a toned-syllable

The profile in (22) is generated using sequences such as those in (21a). It covers all five possible contexts in terms of tones preceding a neutral-toned syllable. Such a move is justified by the fact that all Zuoquan tones end in a fall (recall (5)),¹¹ so that the tonal context preceding the neutral-toned syllable is the same. As can be seen in (22), the general shape of neutral tone syllables is a gentle downward slope starting around the middle of the tone range. Moreover, the variation is very large at every point, as seen by the wide span of each standard deviation at any given point. This is what one would expect for a syllable that did not carry any phonological tone.

Rù does not exhibit any of the behaviors of tone-neutrality as discussed in the preceding paragraphs. Firstly, syllables that carry the Rù tone are all free morphemes and can stand alone (e.g. 筆 [pieʔ] ‘pen’, 哭 [k^huəʔ] ‘cry’). Together with the other tones, Rù is a sandhi trigger for Qù, recall (20a). Finally, Rù has a relatively stable F0 profile, as presented in (23).

¹¹ Excepting Qù-2 as reported in (7b). However, in my fieldwork, all Qù syllables surface consistently as Qù-1 (recall (7b)) when followed by neutral tone syllables. There are no cases where Qù exhibits a F0 profile as described in Wang (1991) in such a context.

(23) The pitch profile of Rù following a toned-syllable

6. Conclusion and implication

Rù must be regarded as a tone category in Zuoquan. Firstly, Rù is phonetically and phonologically distinct from the other tones Yīn Píng, Yáng Píng, Shǎng, and Qù. Secondly, Rù syllables behave differently from toneless ones in Zuoquan, thus Rù is not toneless. Even though I have not offered a tonological description of Zuoquan Rù, one must accept that it is a tone. Figuring out the exact tonal properties of Zuoquan Rù will require an in-depth study of the entire Zuoquan tone system. This is extremely challenging because the patterns are very intricate and confusing. For instance, there are two citation forms for Qù, and the citation forms for Yīn Píng and Shǎng are nearly identical even though they have slightly different sandhi patterns.

Knowing that Rù cannot be collapsed into one of the other tone categories may be an important step towards working out the Zuoquan tonal phonology. At the very least, it prevents certain confusion that would arise if Rù were lumped erroneously with any of the other tones or if it were considered to be toneless.

That Zuoquan Rù is a separate tonal category provides evidence that the ancients probably had not confused syllable structure with tonal properties. Middle Chinese may actually have had 4 different tones. Implications are not only for historical linguistic studies, but also for modern dialectological ones, given the increasing popularity of treating Rù syllables in various Chinese dialects as merely a syllable structural variant of one of other tones.

The case of Zuoquan Rù also puts the spotlight on the possible relationship between syllable codas and tone. Morén & Zsiga (2006) suggest that glottal plosives in Thai codas are pre-linked for a [low] tone feature, even though that feature is not phonetically visible. The F0 profile of Zuoquan Rù certainly does look like corroborating evidence.

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I am grateful to my Zuoquan language consultant who also served as my field guide. Alas, she must remain anonymous. Warm thanks to Lian-Hee Wee for being with me through my struggles with the intriguing Zuoquan tones. May he soon be released from this curse.

左權方言入聲的調性

本文舉證說明左權方言的入聲構成一個獨立的調類。儘管入聲與左權其他四個聲調（陰平、陽平、上聲、去聲）沒有最小對立體，但入聲的單字調、以及在雙音節中的連讀變調規律，與這幾個調均不同。同時，對比左權輕聲無調的表現，入聲也與之不同。這些特徵說明左權入聲應是一個獨立的調類。

方言學研究依據表層互補性，容易視中古漢語入聲為一種音節類型，而非聲調類型。左權入聲的情況提醒我們，過分依賴最小對立體判斷調類，可能會掩蓋音節結構與聲調之間更深層的關係。

關鍵詞：調性，調類，入聲，左權，中古漢語

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Comments for Zhao's "Tonality of the Zuoquan 'Rù'"

This article investigates the phonological status of the short (Ru) tone in the Zuoquan dialect using experimental phonology. The methodological approach is sound, and the data presented are clear and informative.

To further strengthen the paper's impact and coherence, I would like to offer the following suggestions for the author's consideration:

1. The introduction is off-topic. The lengthy discussion of the historical Middle Chinese "Ru" is not relevant to a synchronic analysis. The paper's core question is whether the modern phonetic short tone is phonologically independent. The analysis must be presented strictly within a modern phonological framework, detached from historical terminology.
2. The central thesis argues against a marginal position. The paper spends significant effort arguing that a short tone is phonemically distinct from a long tone. This is the standard, mainstream position in modern phonology and phonetics (e.g., as seen in all *Journal of the International Phonetic Association* illustrations of Chinese dialects). Framing the paper as a rebuttal to a non-standard analysis reduces its novelty. The focus can be shifted to what is new about the Zuoquan data or methodology, not on defending an established premise.
3. The analysis is isolated and therefore provisional. The current study examines the Ru tone in isolation, which limits the interpretability of its phonological behavior. Presenting the complete tonal inventory and tone sandhi patterns would provide necessary context and allow for a more robust, systematic analysis. Expanding the scope in future work is essential to validate and deepen the phonological conclusions drawn here.

In summary, the empirical foundation of the study is solid. To enhance its scholarly impact, revisions should focus on refining the paper's framework, clarifying its theoretical positioning, and expanding its empirical scope to encompass the broader tonal system of Zuoquan.

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Response to Comments for “Tonality of the Zuoquan ‘Rù’”

Kaixin Zhao

Hong Kong Baptist University

22482946@life.hkbu.edu.hk

It is a great thing to be able to respond to reviews candidly, especially to reviews so kindly and instructively given. It is a pity that the reviewer has chosen to remain anonymous, for I would have very much like to express my gratitude unambiguously.

There are three main points in the review. The first two appear to me to originate from a single framework of thought: the status of Rù as a tone following Middle Chinese categorization. To my understanding, scholars of the *yīnyùnxué* (音韻學) tradition (philologists and dialectologists included) regard Rù as a tonal category based on archived documents that classified Rù as one of the four *shēngs* 四聲 (interpreted as “tone”). These assumptions require qualification among theoretical tonologists. To anyone outside the Chinese philological tradition, a CVV syllable and a CVX syllable with the same pitch melody would have the same tone but different syllable structure. My introduction may feel excessive to anyone familiar with Middle Chinese doctrines. Theoreticians in other areas of phonology are less likely to understand the motivation of the research question without this philological context.

On the second point, the reviewer writes “short tone is phonemically distinct from a long tone”. Given that these Chinese short tones are all from closed syllables, the shortness is not primitive but derives from syllable structure. We know this because the Rù syllables are not monomoraic CV syllables where things are just short. They are always closed by obstruents, and are standalone monosyllabic words, which suggests bimoraicity. As such, what is phonemically contrastive is not necessarily tone. A null hypothesis would be to attribute contrast to the segmental phonology if the pitches overlap. For example, in Cantonese, [si33] and [sit3] have overlapping pitches but clearly different segmental make-up. It is more reasonable to say that the tones are the same, but the contrast is in the syllable structure. The reviewer kindly referred to the illustrations of Chinese languages in the *Journal of the International Phonetic Association*. In this regard, my understanding was that the illustrations did not claim whether the contrasts came as a result of tone length or of syllable structure. For instance, in Zee’s (1991) illustration for Cantonese, while 9 tones were listed, it was also evident that he had no minimal pairs in terms of syllables. It would be fairer to think that Zee was being faithful to the phonetic data than to assume he had taken a position as to what was phonemically contrastive.

While we may rely only on archived documents for languages of the past, analysis of modern living languages requires real arguments for the establishment of Rù as a tone category. My paper provides those arguments based on actual phonetic and phonological patterning. These override the apparent pitch similarity to argue that the segmental differences do not adequately capture the contrasts I presented. An audacious suggestion that I might make is that all claims of Rù’s tonality in modern Chinese languages need to undergo similarly rigorous search for evidence.

The final critique is that my analysis is isolated and provisional. I agree. I have looked only at the Rù of Zuoquan and not of the entire Zuoquan tone system. In fact, I have noted in the paper that I have not proposed what the Rù tone in Zuoquan looks like. There are indeed many other issues in Zuoquan which may impact on what the phonological representation of the Zuoquan Rù would be. I am unable to discuss them in the present paper. However, it is irrefutable, given the evidence presented, that Rù is a separate category, and that it is tonal in nature. Any developments will have to be congruent with this conclusion.

I would like to add that this case of Zuoquan is a black swan (Taleb 2007). While some Chinese dialects may present Rù syllables that are reducible to other tone categories, we now have a case in Zuoquan on the reality of tone that may be masked by segmental phonology.

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The Distribution of Nasal Codas across Chinese Dialects and its Implication

Pauline Bolin Liu

Hong Kong Baptist University

paulinelbolin@gmail.com

Abstract

This study examines the distribution of nasal codas across Chinese dialects, focusing on (i) the combinations of nasal codas with different vowels, such as [i] and [a], and (ii) the contrasts between nasal codas in different vowel contexts. The results from a survey showed different relative frequencies of vowel-nasal combinations, with [-n] more frequent than [-ŋ] and [-m] in the [i_] context while [-ŋ] more frequent than [-n] and [-m] in the [a_] context. For nasal codas at different places, their contrasts are generally more frequent in the [a_] context than in the [i_] context. The results indicated that a phonological contrast exhibited different distributional properties in different phonetic contexts.

Keywords: distribution, nasal coda, contrast, Chinese dialects

1. Introduction

1.1 Nasals across Chinese dialects

Nasals widely exist in world languages and across Chinese dialects (Maddieson, 1984; Lee & Zee, 2010, 2014; Gordon, 2016; Li, 2023). Cross-linguistically, for example, all the 317 languages surveyed by Maddieson (1984) preserve nasal contrasts, with two-way contrasts existing in 31.9% out of the total, three-way contrasts in 30.0%, and four-way contrasts in 26.2%. The dental/alveolar (95.3%) and bilabial (94.3%) nasals were the two most frequent nasals of the languages in Maddieson (1984).

In Chinese dialects, different patterns were observed for nasal onsets and nasal codas. For nasal onsets, the bilabial [m-] was observed to be the most frequent, followed by the velar [ŋ-] and the alveolar [n-] (Lee & Zee, 2010, 2014; Ye, 2011; Li, 2023). For example, Li (2023) surveyed 201 Chinese dialects, and discovered that the bilabial [m-] (99.5%) was the most frequent nasal onset. The velar onset [ŋ-] (83.6%) and the alveolar [n-] (80.1%) had similar frequencies. For nasal codas, on the other hand, velar nasal [-ŋ] turned out to be more frequent than the alveolar [-n] and the bilabial [-m] at syllable-final position across Chinese dialects (Lee & Zee, 2010, 2014).

1.2 Consonantal contrasts and vowel contexts

Human language systems were observed to prefer more distinct sound pairs (Lindblom & Maddieson, 1988; Flemming, 2004, 2013). In speech, the articulatory and perceptual properties of a consonant could be influenced by its neighbouring vowels because of coarticulation (Lieberman et al., 1967; Sereno et al., 1987). Experimental studies in the literature showed that the identification of a consonant is less accurate in some vowel contexts than in others (Winitz et al., 1972; Lee-Kim, 2014). Relevant to this, the perceptual distinctiveness between two contrastive consonants might also be influenced by their vowel contexts (Li & Zhang, 2017, 2023). For example, sibilant place contrasts (e.g., [s] vs. [ʃ]) were found to be less frequent in the [i] context than in the [a] context cross-linguistically (Lee-Kim, 2014) and in Chinese dialects (Li & Zhang, 2017; Li, 2021). In perception, earlier experimental studies observed that sibilant contrasts were perceptually less distinct in the [i] context than in the [a] context

(Li & Zhang, 2017, 2023). Similarly, the contrast of alveolar sonorants [n] vs. [l] is also found to be less frequent (Li, 2023) and perceptually less distinct (Liu & Li, 2024a) in the [i_] context than in the [a_] context.

For nasal codas, experimental studies observed that different nasals had a smaller articulatory difference (Guan, 2019; Faytak et al., 2020) and perceptual distinction (Faytak et al., 2020; Chen & Guion-Anderson, 2011) in the [i_] context than in other vowel contexts (e.g., [a_]). In Shanghai Mandarin, for example, the results from ultrasound investigation (Faytak et al., 2020) showed that the contrast of [-n] vs. [-ŋ] as codas is consistently neutralized in the [i_] context; on the other hand, the contrast of [-n] vs. [-ŋ] is not neutralized in the low vowel [a_] context. In a follow-up AXB experiment, Faytak et al. (2020) observed that Shanghai Mandarin listeners and Standard Mandarin listeners alike could not distinguish the [in] vs. [iŋ] contrast in Shanghai Mandarin, which echoed the results from the ultrasound experiment that Shanghai Mandarin speakers could not distinguish [in] vs. [iŋ] in production (Faytak et al., 2020). Similarly, a perceptual experiment by Chen and Guion-Anderson (2011) tested the identification of nasal codas in different vowel contexts (i.e., [i_], [ə_], [a_]) by native Southern Min listeners and native Standard Mandarin listeners. The two dialects differ in their inventories of nasal codas, whereby Southern Min has all the three nasal codas [-m, -n, -ŋ] while Mandarin has two [-n, -ŋ]. For each group of participants, the stimuli in the perceptual experiment were real words in their native language, including three nasal codas (i.e., [-m, -n, -ŋ]) for Southern Min listeners and two (i.e., [-n, -ŋ]) for Standard Mandarin listeners. The results showed that, the two groups of listeners both have lower accuracies in the high-front vowel [i_] context than other vowel contexts (i.e., [ə_], [a_]).

1.3 This study

Studies in the literature showed that the relative frequencies of onset consonantal contrasts are influenced by its vowel contexts (Lee-Kim, 2014; Li & Zhang, 2017; Li, 2021, 2023; Zhang & Li, 2022). For example, the contrasts of nasal onsets are less frequently observed in the [i_] context than in the [a_] context (Li, 2023). In terms of nasal codas, it was observed that the velar nasal [-ŋ] is more frequent than [-n, -m] at the syllable-final position across Chinese dialects (Lee & Zee, 2010, 2014). On the other hand, it remains to uncover if the distribution of nasal codas differs across vowel contexts, such as [i_] vs. [a_]. This study focused on the distributional properties of nasal codas in different vowel contexts across Chinese dialects, aiming to answer the following research questions, as given in (1).

- (1) Research Questions
 - i. Do nasal codas have the same relative frequencies in different vowel contexts? E.g. is the velar [-ŋ] more frequent than [-m] and [-n] in both the [i_] and [a_] contexts?
 - ii. Do different vowel contexts influence the presence/absence of the contrasts of nasal codas at different places? Specifically, is the contrast of nasal codas at different places less frequent in the [i_] context than in the [a_] context?

Sound patterns from crosslinguistic typologies can reveal general tendencies in the properties of human sound systems (Maddieson, 1984, 2018; Hyman, 2008, 2012; Clements, 2009; Kiparsky, 2018), which can be referred to in generalizing phonological grammar (Steriade, 2001). An attempt is made in this study based on the results of the survey.

2. Materials

To answer the two research questions above, a survey was conducted focusing on the distributional patterns of nasal codas across Chinese dialects. The materials were a total of 202 articles collected from the journal *Fangyan* 方言 [*Dialects*] published during 1979~2020, which described the inventories and phonotactics of consonants and vowels of each dialect. These 202 dialects are distributed across different dialectal groups, including Cantonese, Xiang, Gan, etc.

The current study focuses on the combinations of nasal codas [-m, -n, -ŋ] and two different vowels [i] and [a], with a total of six rimes including [-im, -in, -iŋ, -am, -an, -aŋ]. Among the 202 Chinese dialects, Yixian 黟縣 (Li, 2018) was excluded because it does not include [i] in its rime inventory, and Xingxian 興縣 (Shi & Zhang, 2014) was excluded because it does not have the rime [a]. Therefore, the survey was based on the remaining 200 dialects which include [i] and [a] in their rime inventories.

3. Nasal codas and vowel contexts

This section reports the distribution of rimes with nasal codas across Chinese dialects. Below (2) presents the token numbers of rimes with nasal codas and their percentage out of 200 Chinese dialects. As a general observation, nasal codas are slightly less frequent in the [i_] context (206 tokens) than in the [a_] context (245 tokens) across Chinese dialects. To be more specific, the 200 Chinese dialects have an average of 1.03 tokens of rimes with nasal codas in the [i_] context, and an average of 1.22 tokens of rimes with nasal codas in the [a_] context.

- (2) The distribution of rimes with nasal codas across 200 Chinese dialects
 a. [i_] context

	Pattern	Token number	Percentage	Example dialect
i	-im	31	15.5%	Binyang 賓陽 (Mo, 2014)
ii	-in	101	50.5%	Cangwu 蒼梧 (Zhong, 2015)
iii	-iŋ	74	37.0%	Badu 八都 (Mai, 2008)
	Total	206		

- b. [a_] context

	Pattern	Token number	Percentage	Example dialect
i	-am	33	16.5%	Changtai 長泰 (Xu, 2018)
ii	-an	80	40.0%	Hua'an 華安 (Xu, 2020)
iii	-aŋ	132	66.0%	Rongxian 容縣 (Chen, 1999)
	Total	245		

As shown in (2) above, the three nasal codas have different relative frequencies in (2a) for context [i_] and (2b) for [a_]. For the [i_] context, the relative frequencies of nasal codas showed a decreasing order of [-n] > [-ŋ] > [-m], as in (2a). Of the three relevant rimes, [-in] exists in more than half of the relevant dialects (101 dialects, 50.5%), being the most frequent among the three, such as Cangwu 蒼梧 (Zhong, 2015); 74 dialects have [-iŋ] in their rime inventories, equal to 37.0% of the total, e.g., Badu 八都 (Mai, 2008); 31 dialects (15.5%) allow the [-im], being the least frequent one, such as Binyang 賓陽 (Mo, 2014).

For the [a_] context, on the other hand, the relative frequencies of nasal codas are in a

decreasing order of [-ŋ] > [-n] > [-m], as presented in (2b). The rime [-aŋ] turned out to be the most frequent (132 dialects, 66.0%), followed by [-an] appearing in 80 dialects (40.0%). The least frequent one is [-am], existing in only 33 dialects (16.5%), such as Rongxian 容縣 (Chen, 1999).

Below (3) displays the number of dialects involving each nasal coda in both [i_] and [a_] contexts, e.g., a dialect including [-im, -am] in its rime inventory, and the percentage across Chinese dialects. Across the 200 dialects, [-in] and [-aŋ] co-exist in 70 dialects (35.0%), e.g., Hua'an 華安 (Xu, 2020); 59 dialects (29.5%) have [-in, -an], e.g., Fenghuang 鳳凰 (Li, 2011); 30 dialects (15.0%) have [-im, -am], e.g., Binyang 賓陽 (Mo, 2014).

(3) The distribution of rimes with nasal codas in both [i_] and [a_] contexts

	Pattern	No. of dialects	Percentage	Example dialect
i	-im -am	30	15.0%	Hua'an 華安 (Xu, 2020)
ii	-in -an	59	29.5%	Fenghuang 鳳凰 (Li, 2011)
iii	-iŋ -aŋ	70	35.0%	Binyang 賓陽 (Mo, 2014)

Before reporting the patterns of nasal codas, a few notes need to be given to the dialects that do not have rimes with a nasal coda in the [i_] or [a_] contexts among the 200 Chinese dialects. In the [i_] context, 45 dialects (22.5%) do not have rimes such as [-im] [-in] or [-iŋ], e.g., Fuliang 浮梁 (Xie, 2011); in the [a_] context, 54 dialects (27.0%) do not have rimes such as [-am] [-an] or [-aŋ], e.g., Dangtu 當塗 (Zheng et al., 2012). As the intersection of these two types, a total of 23 dialects (11.5%) do not include any of the relevant six rimes ([-im, -in, -iŋ, -am, -an, -aŋ]) in their sound systems, such as Chenxi 辰溪 (Xie, 2010).

4. Vowel-coda combinations

This section focuses on the combinations of vowel and nasal coda. The dialects to focus on are those with one nasal coda following the vowel [i/a], i.e., one-way nasal coda system. The distribution of one-way nasal coda system across Chinese dialects was displayed in (4) below. In general, the one-way nasal coda system is more frequent in the [i_] context (112 dialects, 56.0%) than in the [a_] context (72 dialects, 36.0%).

(4) One-way nasal coda system across Chinese dialects

a. [i_] context

	Pattern	No. of dialects	Percentage	Example dialect
i	-im	0	0	/
ii	-in	61	30.5%	Meihua 梅花 (Shen & Zhou, 2017)
iii	-iŋ	51	25.5%	Fuyang 阜陽 (Wang, 2012)
	Total	112	56.0%	

b. [a_] context

	Pattern	No. of dialects	Percentage	Example dialect
i	-am	0	0	/
ii	-an	12	6.0%	Anqing 安慶 (Bao, 2012)
iii	-aŋ	60	30.0%	Changshu 常熟 (Yuan, 2010)
	Total	72	36.0%	

For the [i_] context in (4a), 61 dialects (30.5%) only have the rime [-in], excluding [-im, -iŋ], such as Meihua 梅花 (Shen & Zhou, 2017); 51 dialects (25.5%) only have the rime [-iŋ], without [-im, -in], e.g., Fuyang 阜陽 (Wang, 2012). For the [a_] context, as in (4biii), 60 dialects have [-aŋ] only, e.g., Changshu 常熟 (Yuan, 2010), accounting for 30.0% of the total; 12 dialects (6.0%) have [-an] only, e.g., Anqing 安慶 (Bao, 2012).

In both contexts, none of the relevant Chinese dialects preserves the bilabial nasal coda [-m] alone, as presented in (4ai) and (4bi). This is reminiscent of the observations in the survey by Lee and Zee (2014) that no Chinese dialect has only one nasal coda [-m] without considering the vowel contexts.

5. Contrast of nasal codas

This section examines the contrasts of nasal codas across different places. The patterns are reported first for the dialects with two nasal codas, i.e., two-way nasal contrast, and then for those with three nasal codas.

5.1 Two-way nasal coda system

Below, (5) shows the distribution of two-way nasal coda contrasts of [-n vs. -ŋ], [-m vs. -ŋ] and [-m vs. -n] in different vowel contexts. In general, two-way nasal coda contrasts differed in their relative frequencies in the [i_] and [a_] contexts.

(5) Two-way nasal coda system across Chinese dialects

a. [-n vs. -ŋ] contrast

	Contrast	No. of dialects	Percentage	Example dialect
i	-in -iŋ	12	6.0%	Wu'ning 武寧 (Zhong, 2004)
ii	-an -aŋ	41	20.5%	Fenghuang 鳳凰 (Li, 2011)

b. [-m vs. -ŋ] contrast

	Contrast	No. of dialects	Percentage	Example dialect
i	-im -iŋ	3	1.5%	Ningde 寧德 (Sha, 1999)
ii	-am -aŋ	6	3.0%	Haikou 海口 (Du, 2007)

c. [-m vs. -n] contrast

	Contrast	No. of dialects	Percentage	Example dialect
i	-im -in	20	10.0%	Cangwu 蒼梧 (Zhong, 2015)
ii	-am -an	2	1.0%	Huaiji 懷集 (Yang, 2012)

As presented in (5a) and (5b), the two-way contrast of [-n vs. -ŋ] and that of [-m vs. -ŋ] appear less frequently in the [i_] context than in the [a_] context. For the [-n vs. -ŋ] contrast, as shown in (5a), 12 dialects (6.0%) have a [-in vs. -iŋ] contrast, without [-am], e.g., Wu'ning 武寧 (Zhong, 2004); 41 dialects (20.5%) have a [-an vs. -aŋ] contrast, without [-am], e.g., Fenghuang 鳳凰 (Li, 2011). For the [-m vs. -ŋ] contrast, as in (5b), only three dialects (1.5%) allow a [-im vs. -iŋ] contrast, e.g., Ningde 寧德 (Sha, 1999); six dialects have a [-am vs. -aŋ] contrast, e.g., Haikou 海口 (Du, 2007), taking up 3.0% of the total.

On the other hand, the [-m vs. -n] contrast is more frequent in the [i_] context than in the [a_] context, as shown in (5c). For the [i_] context, 20 dialects (10.0%) have a [-im vs. -in]

contrast, such as Cangwu 蒼梧 (Zhong, 2015); for the [a_] context, only two dialects (1.0%) have a [-am vs. -an] contrast, e.g., Huaiji 懷集 (Yang, 2012).

When comparing the [i_] and [a_] contexts, the two-way nasal coda contrasts are less frequent in the [i_] context than in the [a_] context. For the [i_] context, as in (5ai, 5bi, and 5ci), 35 dialects (12+3+20) have two-way nasal coda contrasts, equal to 17.5% of the total; for the [a_] context, as in (5aai, 5bii, and 5cii), 49 dialects (41+6+2) have two-way nasal contrasts, adding up to 24.5% of the 200 dialects.

5.2 Three-way nasal coda system

Below, (6) reports the three-way contrast of [-im vs. -in vs. -iŋ] and [-am vs. -an vs. -aŋ] across 200 Chinese dialects. As a general observation, the three-way contrast of codas [-m vs. -n vs. -ŋ] is not common for both [i_] and [a_] contexts across Chinese dialects, with the [-im vs. -in vs. -iŋ] contrast less frequent than the [-am vs. -an vs. -aŋ] contrast.

For the [i_] context, only eight dialects have the [-im vs. -in vs. -iŋ] contrast (4.0%), such as Hua'an 華安 (Xu, 2020). For the [a_] context, 25 dialects preserve a three-way contrast of nasal coda, i.e., [-am vs. -an vs. -aŋ], taking up 12.5% of the total 200 dialects, such as Changtai 長泰 (Xu, 2018).

(6) Three-way nasal coda system across Chinese dialects

	Contrast	No. of dialects	Percentage	Example dialect
i	-im -in -iŋ	8	4.0%	Hua'an 華安 (Xu, 2020)
ii	-am -an -aŋ	25	12.5%	Changtai 長泰 (Xu, 2018)

As shown in (6) above, the three-way contrast of nasal codas is less frequent in the [i_] context than in the [a_] context. This is consistent with the observations in Section 5.1 that two-way contrasts of nasal codas (i.e., [-n vs. -ŋ], [-m vs. -ŋ], [-m vs. -n]) are generally less frequent in the [i_] than in the [a_] context. Below (7) provides more details on the dialects that have a three-way contrast of nasal codas. Eight dialects have a three-way contrast of nasal codas in both [i_] and [a_] contexts, such as Hua'an 華安 (Xu, 2020) as in (7i). Another 17 dialects (16+1) have a three-way contrast in the [a_] context, but not in the [i_] context, as in (7ii) and (7iii). That is, 16 dialects have a two-way [-im vs. -in] contrast, such as Binyang 賓陽 (Mo, 2014); one dialect does not have any of the relevant rimes with nasal coda in the [i_] context, i.e., Wenchang 文昌 (Liang, 1986). Taken together the observations in (6) and (7), a three-way contrast of [-im vs. -in vs. -iŋ] implies a [-am vs. -an vs. -aŋ] contrast across the 200 Chinese dialects.

(7) Three-way contrast of nasal codas in [i_] or [a_] context

	[a_]	[i_]	No. of dialects (%)	Example dialect
i	-am -an -aŋ	-im -in -iŋ	8 (4.0%)	Hua'an 華安 (Xu, 2020)
ii	-am -an -aŋ	-im -in	16 (8.0%)	Binyang 賓陽 (Mo, 2014)
iii	-am -an -aŋ	N.A.	1 (0.5%)	Wenchang 文昌 (Liang, 1986)

6. Discussion

6.1 The combination of nasal segments

As reported in Section 3, the distribution of nasal codas turned out to differ in the [i_] vs. [a_] contexts across Chinese dialects. As a quick summary, different patterns showed up in these two vowel contexts, in a decreasing order of relative frequencies:

- (8) Relative frequencies of the combination of vowels and nasal codas (in decreasing order)
- a. [i_] context: -in (50.5%) > -iŋ (37.0%) > -im (15.5%)
(i.e. the combination [-in] is more frequent than [-iŋ], and [-iŋ] is more frequent than [-im], where > marks the decreasing order of relative frequency)
 - b. [a_] context: -aŋ (66.0%) > -an (40.0%) > -am (16.5%)
(i.e. the combination [-aŋ] is more frequent than [-an], and [-an] is more frequent than [-am])

As stated in (8), the vowels differ in the relative frequencies of their combinations with the alveolar [-n] and the velar [-ŋ], with [-in] (50.5%) more frequent than [-iŋ] (37.0%) while [-aŋ] (66.0%) more frequent than [-an] (40.0%). These detailed differences suggest that the combinations of segments should be considered as a factor when evaluating the relative frequencies of segments.

Previous studies showed the relative frequencies, a decreasing order, of [m-] > [ŋ-] and [n-] as onsets (Li, 2023) and [-ŋ] > [-n] and [-m] as codas (Lee & Zee, 2010, 2014). Assuming a connection between typology and phonology, these two patterns seem to indicate potential orderings of preferences as in (9), if expressed as constraint rankings in the framework of Optimality Theory (McCarthy & Prince, 1993; Prince & Smolensky, 2004).

- (9) Constraint rankings of nasal onsets and nasal codas
- a. *#ŋ » *#n » *#m
 - b. *m# » *n# » *ŋ#
- (Notes: * marks a prohibited structure; # marks syllable boundary; » marks that the constraint to its left is higher ranked.)

When considering the combinations of vowel and nasal codas, the distributional properties observed in this study seem to suggest the ranking of constraints as in (10), when focusing on codas alone. The validity of these potential constraints and rankings awaits the verification of further studies.

- (10) Constraint rankings of rimes with nasal codas
- a. *im# » *iŋ# » *in#
 - b. *am# » *aŋ# » *aŋ#

6.2 The contrasts of nasal segments

Extensive studies in the literature have observed that, for two segments, the presence of contrasts may differ across phonetic contexts (Steriade, 2008; Lee-Kim, 2014; Li & Zhang, 2017; Liu & Li, 2024a, b, among others). For nasal onsets, in particular, it is observed that place contrasts are more frequently observed in the [i_] context than in the [a_] context (Li, 2023). Similar patterns are observed in this study about the contrast of nasal codas, as reported

in Section 5. For the contrasts of [-n vs. -ŋ] and [-m vs. -n], for example, the relative frequencies are re-summarized in (11).

- (11) Relative frequencies of nasal coda contrasts (in decreasing order)
- a. [-n] vs. [-ŋ]: [a_] context > [i_] context
 - b. [-m] vs. [-n]: [i_] context > [a_] context

Among various theoretical frameworks, P-Map (Steriade, 2001, 2008) considers the relative distinctiveness of a phonological contrast across different phonetic contexts. For example, a [s] vs. [ʂ] contrast is more distinct in the V_V context than in the C_C context (Steriade, 2001). For the contrast of nasal codas, the different patterns as summarized in (11) above seem to suggest the rankings of constraints shown in (12), following P-Map.

- (12) Constraint rankings of nasal coda contrasts
- a. $\Delta(n-\eta)/a_ \# > \Delta(n-\eta)/i_ \#$
(i.e. the [n] vs. [ŋ] contrast is more different in the [a_] context than in the [i_] context, where Δ = difference)
 - b. $\Delta(m-n)/i_ \# > \Delta(m-n)/a_ \#$
(i.e. the [m] vs. [n] contrast is more different in the in the [i_] context than in the [a_] context)

Of these two rankings, (12a) can find its phonetic basis from the results of experimental studies in the literature. For example, nasals are found to have a smaller difference in the [i_] context than in other vowel contexts, in terms of articulatory gestures (Guan, 2019; Faytak et al., 2020) and perceptual distinction (Faytak et al., 2020; Chen & Guion-Anderson, 2021). On the other hand, the suggestion in (12b) needs the verification of future empirical investigations, as to the detailed potential interactions of nasal pairs and vowel contexts.

7. Conclusions

This study examines the distributional patterns of nasal coda in different vowel contexts across Chinese dialects. The results showed that the nasal codas have different distributional patterns in the [i_] and [a_] contexts across Chinese dialects. For the [i_] context, the alveolar [-n] is the most frequent; for the [a_] context, [-ŋ] turns out to be the most frequent. In terms of nasal coda contrasts, the [i_] context generally preserve fewer contrasts than the [a_] context. This echoed the observations about nasal onsets in the literature that the contrasts of nasal onsets are less frequent in the [i_] context than in the [a_] contexts (Li, 2023). The distributional patterns were taken as indications of general tendencies in the sound systems of human languages, in terms of the combinations of vowel and nasal codas and the contrast of nasal codas. For both aspects, it is suggested that different patterns might occur across different phonetic contexts.

This study has a few limitations. First, for tonal languages such as Chinese, tones contribute to phonological contrasts, for example, [ma] with a high-level tone indicating ‘mother’ and with a falling tone indicating ‘to scold’. For the same segmental contrast, such as onset /n-/ vs. /l-/ in different vowel contexts, different conclusions could be arrived at when tone is considered in the evaluation of contrast (Liu & Li, 2024b) vs. when tone is not considered (Li, 2023). In the current study, tones were not examined when exploring the distributional properties of nasal coda contrasts across Chinese dialects. More detailed investigation could explore if nasal coda contrasts have different relative frequencies when considering tones. Second, this study was based on the rimes across relevant dialects. An

Second, this study was based on the rimes across relevant dialects. An expanded study could examine the nasal coda contrasts between monosyllabic morphemes, which are usually in the form of CVN syllables, e.g., [tam vs. tan]. Third, this study is limited to the description of different systems of nasal codas. It remains relatively unclear what phonetic properties contribute to the contrasts of nasal codas in different sound systems, which awaits further experimental studies.

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漢語方言中鼻音韻尾的分佈及其意義

本研究關注漢語方言中鼻音韻尾在不同元音環境的類型。結果顯示，在高元音[i_]環境中，鼻音韻尾的頻率由高到低依次為[-n]，[-ŋ]，[-m]；而在低元音[a_]環境中，鼻音約為的頻率由高到低依次是[-ŋ]，[-n]，[-m]。當比較不同的元音環境時，鼻音韻尾的對立在[i_]環境中相對較少，而在[a_]環境中相對較多。這些結果顯示，語音環境對輔音的分佈和對立有影響。

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《漢語方言中鼻音韻尾的分佈及其意義》評審報告

該論文對鼻音與元音的匹配類型在漢語方言中的表現做了調查，得出了若干鼻音在音節開頭或結尾位置出現概率情況的結論。論證比較清晰，結論提供了有趣的觀察視角。但以下表述尚需澄清：

Taken together the observations in (6) and (7), a three-way contrast of [-im vs. -in vs. -iŋ] might be a pre-requisite of a [-am vs. -an vs. -aŋ] contrast across the 200 Chinese dialects (§5.2 Three-way nasal coda system, p. 6).

5.2 小節前半部分論證：「鼻尾韻的三重對比在[i_]語境中出現的頻率低於[a_]語境。這與第 5 節的觀察結果一致：鼻尾韻的二重對比（即[-n vs. -ŋ]、[-m vs. -ŋ]、[-m vs. -n]）在[i_]語境中通常比[a_]語境更少見。（頁 6）」（由評審翻譯）那麼，也就是說鼻音在音節尾位置出現在[i_]比[a_]少。既然如此，為什麼該文卻得出結論說：出現少的形式是出現多的形式的先決條件？一般情況下出現多的形式才是出現少的形式的先決條件。此處表達不清楚，所謂「先決條件」指什麼需要更多解釋。

此外，該論文所涉獵的相關假設在文中都有論述，但是缺乏聲學原理的論證視角，使得很多解釋捨近求遠。比如結論部分提到：「在[i_]環境中，齒齶音[-n]最為常見；而在[a_]環境中，[-ŋ]則更為普遍。（頁 8）」（由評審翻譯）從聲學角度看，這跟音與音的匹配有關。[i_]與齒齶音[-n]發音部位接近，開口度也近似，是比較容易匹配發音的；而[a_]和後鼻音[-ŋ]開口度近似，舌位也容易銜接，所以結合更為普遍。同樣，[a_]與[-m]的不匹配也是聲學原因導致的，[a_]開口度最大，[-m]開口度最小，非常不匹配。

論文開始在介紹前人的研究結果時提到：「雙唇音[m-]（99.5%）是鼻音起始頻率最高的音。……軟齶鼻音[-ŋ]在各漢語方言中比齒齶音[-n]和雙唇音[-m]更常見，且多出現在音節末位置。（頁 1）」（由評審翻譯）這也可以從聲學角度去分析：雙唇音[m-]出現在音節開頭是非常合理的，因為從未發音時的口腔閉合狀態過渡到發雙唇閉合音[m-]是非常自然的銜接；而在音節結尾處，軟齶鼻音[-ŋ]又是與之前的開口元音最匹配的結合。這也是為什麼大多數北方方言裏處於音節開頭的[m-]最常見，而處於韻尾的[-m]卻丟失了。同樣，大多數北方方言中軟齶鼻音[ŋ]出現在音節開頭只有殘留，出現在音節末尾卻保留得比較多。聲學是解釋語音現象的一個重要視角，文章在調查基礎上應引入多角度的解釋。

最後一個問題是關於調查對象的，論文結論建立在對《方言》中 200 篇論文的語料基礎上，不是第一手資料。這雖然可以一定程度上用數量彌補，但仍然有問題，因為讀者不知道這些文章是音系的全面介紹，還是只是對方言中出現的部分語音現象進行的不全面描述。如果是後者，那麼就會動搖討論的基礎。因此對於語料來源是如何甄別的應有更詳細的交代。

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Perception of Coda Stop Voicing by Hong Kong English Listeners

Philip Chung Yeung
Hong Kong Baptist University
philipyeeung@life.hkbu.edu.hk

Abstract

This study investigates how Hong Kong English (HKE) listeners perceive coda stop voicing by varying vowel duration and release burst spectral cues in different places of articulation. Cantonese-speaking participants completed two perceptual tasks with five-step continua for each cue. Results reveal sensitivity to both temporal and spectral cues in alveolar stops, with significant effects for vowel length and burst quality. Findings highlight possible place-specific cue utilisation in perception among Hong Kong English users and suggest a potential specific strategy with mixed cue usage among Hong Kong English users in differentiating coda voicing.

Keywords: burst spectrum, vowel duration, coda voicing, Hong Kong English, L2 perception

1. Introduction

1.1 Coda voicing in Hong Kong English contexts

The perception and production of Hong Kong speakers of English are influenced by their native Cantonese (Hung 2000; Ting & Wong 2018; Wee 2008, 2018; Wee & Cheung 2014; Wong 2018). Transference from Cantonese to English contributes to the localised, Cantonese-coloured English, which may be referred to as “Hong Kong English” (hereinafter HKE). Previous studies found HKE users’ inconsistencies in sound perception and production led to difficulties in some easily confused sound pairs (Chan 2010, 2011; Wong 2018). Such inconsistencies can be attributed to the absence of sound contrasts in the Cantonese sound inventory, which influences HKE users’ sound perception to perceive certain sounds in English differently. These influences may have driven HKE users to develop a particular set of perceptual cues to overcome constraints imposed by their native Cantonese.

HKE differs systematically in production in contexts where standard English varieties typically show coda release. To illustrate, Setter et al. (2015) showed that HKE speakers elided coda with no audible release of the [d] plosive across all five diphthongs, tabled in (1).

(1) Comparison of /...d/ coda between BrE and HKE speakers

Variety	/...d/	Syllable Nucleus	Perceived Outputs
HKE	Elided	$\begin{array}{c} N_{\text{lengthened}} \\ \wedge \\ a \quad I \end{array}$	<i>side</i> perceived as <i>sigh</i> (no audible release of [d])
BrE	Retained	$\begin{array}{c} N_{\text{shortened}} \\ \wedge \\ a \quad I \end{array}$	<i>side</i> and <i>sigh</i> perceived as distinct

Coda [d] is elided in words such as *side* and compensated by a lengthened nucleus with diphthong [a:], yielding [sa:] so that *side* becomes homophonous with *sigh*. This example

highlights the two kinds of differences between Cantonese and English that must be kept in view when studying HKE speakers with a native Cantonese background: (i) the consonantal inventory, and (ii) the existing phonemic contrasts; crucially noting that (i) may have an impact on (ii).

With respect to (i), Cantonese does not feature voicing contrasts but only voiceless obstruents, namely [p], [t], and [k] for plosives (Edge 1991; Cheung et al. 2024; see also Chan 2011 for challenges in English fricative contrasts by HKE speakers). The impact of the inventory constrains them in closing words with voiced obstruents. Therefore, accurate distinctions in specific English sound contrasts, such as [p] vs. [b], may not apply to Cantonese speakers since Cantonese speakers face a conflict between their L1 constraints and English target forms. This L1 phonotactic gap likely shapes HKE listeners' reliance on alternative cues for coda voicing differentiation.

With respect to (ii), English and Cantonese voicing are realised differently. At the risk of Anglocentricity, [voice] is used to refer to plosives that involve vocal fold vibration during closure, and [aspiration] to refer to plosives that have an evident burst after the point of release. Cantonese and English realise contrasts in separate dimensions. English contrasts are divided by [-voice] and [+voice] in the VOT continuum. Voicing is then distinguished in a two-way contrast by a negative to very short positive VOT lag as voiced, and a longer VOT lag as voiceless. In Cantonese, plosive contrast is cued spectrally after the point of plosive release between the nucleus and the coda plosive and is divided by [-aspiration] and [+aspiration], also in a two-way contrast. For [-aspiration], a compact burst is observed, while intense and high-frequency frication is observed for [+aspiration] in the release burst spectrogram. These phonemic differences highlight potential perceptual mismatches for HKE and may lead to HKE-specific cue strategies in coda stop perception.

1.2 Coda stop voicing insights from non-native English speakers

Perception and production of coda voicing research revealed that non-native (including L2) English listeners demonstrate distinct cue reliance patterns compared to native speakers when processing identical voicing contrasts (Chan 2011). As for perception, they were found to put less emphasis on utilising spectral cues to differentiate coda voicing. This process was found systematic and can be attributed to the clash between English's underlying voiced-obstruent representation and Cantonese's surface phonetic constraint against word-final voiced obstruents (Eckman 1981). Similarly, Flege's (1995) Speech Learning Model proposes that L1 phonetic categories and constraints influence L2 acquisition with unfamiliar contrasts (e.g., English coda [t]~[d]) found to be challenging when absent in L1.

Various cues are used to perceive coda voicing. Bruggeman et al. (2021) found vowel duration and coda release burst duration to be the prominent cues among non-native English users for contrasting coda voicing. To illustrate, vowel duration tends to be longer before voiced codas, while release burst duration tends to be longer for voiceless codas (Choi et al. 2016). Shattuck-Hufnagel et al. (2011) found voice bars, lengthened vowels, epenthetic vowels, noise, substantial noise, and glottalisation signalled coda stop voicing. These studies demonstrated alternative prominent cue usage among native and non-native English speakers to differentiate coda voicing, and also the context for investigating cue usage among HKE users.

As with many aspects of non-native speech perception, varying L1 phonological experience influences how non-natives weight acoustic cues. Choi et al. (2016) showed that Korean non-native English speakers, whose native vowel inventory is sparsely populated, exhibited reduced sensitivity to formant (F1/F2) differences and instead encoded English coda voicing primarily via vowel duration. Kondaurova and Francis (2008) found that Spanish and Russian learners likewise prioritised duration over spectral quality when perceiving the English

tense-lax contrast. However, only Spanish listeners' reliance on duration correlated with their L1 usage, whereas Russian listeners showed no such transfer. These divergent transfer profiles underscore the need to investigate whether Hong Kong English learners similarly exhibit language-specific cue-weighting patterns or whether they follow a universal temporal-cue bias.

Deriving from all the above, it is given that both Cantonese and Korean do not employ coda voicing distinctions. It is not known whether HKE users would have different cue reliance patterns, with potential variances arising from the city's more extensive English exposure environment (Chan 2004; Deterding et al. 2008). Further exploration is required to clarify how HKE users perceive and interpret coda stop voicing, and enhance our understanding of their perceptual language competence.

The current study attempts to contextualise the perception of coda stop voicing by HKE listeners. Two acoustic cues that are considered most prominent in the literature are focused, i.e., (i) the duration of the vowel preceding the coda stop and (ii) the spectral release burst quality of the coda stops. Based on these two acoustic properties, the research questions this paper addresses are given in (2).

- (2) Research questions
- a. To what extent do HKE listeners rely on the duration of the preceding vowel to differentiate voiced vs. voiceless coda stops?
 - b. To what extent do HKE listeners rely on the spectral properties of coda release bursts to differentiate voiced vs. voiceless coda stops?

2. Methodology

A study of non-native varieties of English such as HKE must not be made using any other variety of English as a reference standard (see Mohanan 1992 for arguments against the comparative fallacy). This means that the design of any perceptual experiments that seek to address the research questions must be based solely on data internal to HKE rather than by reference to British or American standards of coda voicing perception.¹ In order to yield generalisable results, responses are collected from 25 Hong Kong English users who speak Cantonese natively. By treating HKE as a linguistically autonomous variety which features a self-contained phonological system, the methodology adopted here recognises HKE's internal organisational principles and avoids deficit-oriented comparisons.

2.1 Stimuli

The audio stimuli in this experiment were CVC (Consonant-Vowel-Consonant) syllables, in which the final consonants were coda stops. Focusing on two aspects of acoustic properties, the experiment was divided into two parts, namely Part 1 and Part 2. In the vowel duration continua (Part 1), the audio stimuli CVC syllables involved (i) a duration continuum of the middle vowel, and (ii) a coda stop with an ambiguous spectral property between a voiced and a voiceless stop at the same place of articulation. In the release burst continua (Part 2), the audio stimulus CVC syllables involved (i) a vowel with a constant duration, and (ii) a spectral continuum of a coda stop between a voiced and a voiceless stop at the same place of articulation. The procedures for constructing the experimental stimuli are detailed below.

To construct the vowel duration continua, the stimulus words in the experiment were first created based on recordings of the English CVC syllables as listed in (3).

¹ It is neither appropriate nor necessary to use British or American speakers as "control". No variety of English serves as authority to provide the reference baseline.

(3) Words for the recording of stimuli

Place of coda stop \ Voicing of coda stop	Bilabial	Alveolar	Velar
Voiced	<i>cab</i> /kæb/	<i>sad</i> /sæd/	<i>log</i> /lɒg/
Voiceless	<i>cap</i> /kæp/	<i>sat</i> /sæt/	<i>lock</i> /lɒk/

Six words were selected for the experiment. The voiced and the unvoiced minimal pairs were classified into sub-categories in pairs based on the place of articulation of the coda consonant, namely bilabial, alveolar, and velar. As shown in (3), the coda pairs were [p]~[b], [t]~[d] and [k]~[g], and the vowels were [æ] and [ɒ]. The CVC syllables were adopted to reduce the deterrent effect of multi-syllabic words and the effort required to listen to them.

The recordings of the stimuli were obtained from the online text-to-speech engine ImTranslator (Smart Link Corporation 2023) due to the difficulty in finding native English speakers during the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic at the time of research design and experiment preparation. The tokens were recorded using Adobe Audition 2023 through the internal audio mix output function of Microsoft Windows, at a sample rate of 44.1 kHz, at 16-bit bit depth at mono channel.

For the recorded syllables, the durations of the vowels as obtained from the text-to-speech engine are listed in (4). Note that the durations in (4) were each for one token, as the online speech generator provided a single token without a variable for the same word.

(4) Vowel durations in the recorded stimuli tokens (ms)

	Voiceless coda		Voiced coda	
Bilabial	<i>cap</i> /kæp/	176	<i>cab</i> /kæb/	233
Alveolar	<i>sat</i> /sæt/	206	<i>sad</i> /sæd/	278
Velar	<i>lock</i> /lɒk/	172	<i>log</i> /lɒg/	249
	Mean	185	Mean	253

Next, the vowel duration continua are created. The durational difference between the voiceless codas and the voiced codas was aligned with the pattern found in the literature that the duration of vowel tends to be lower when the coda consonant is voiceless and higher when the coda consonant is voiced. In the recorded stimuli, as shown in (4), the mean duration of the vowels before voiceless [p], [t], [k] was 185ms, while that of the vowels before voiced [b], [d], [g] was 253ms. These two durations were used as reference durations for the creation of the vowel duration stimuli.

For the formation of stimuli, three vowel duration continua were created separately for /kæp/~kæb/, /sæt/~sæd/, and /lɒk/~lɒg/, each in five duration steps. In each vowel duration continuum, five duration steps were created as in (5).

(5) Vowel duration values of the vowel duration steps in the vowel duration continua

Steps	Vowel duration at each step (ms)
Step 1	151
Step 2	185
Step 3	219
Step 4	253
Step 5	287

For the vowel duration continua, the different duration steps had an increment of 34ms, which was larger than the just-noticeable difference of duration (Klatt 1976; Kondaurova & Francis 2008). This aimed to ensure that the difference between steps was perceptible.

Manipulation was done on the vowel part using Praat (Boersma & Weenink 2022) with a Praat script (Mitterer 2009). To preserve the acoustic details, vowel portions before the voiced stops (e.g., the vowel [æ] before [b]) were shortened. After treatment, the vowel duration continua were generated with vowel durations that differed in each of the five steps, as in (5).

Subsequently, for the formation of stimuli, three burst spectral continua were created respectively for bilabial [b]~[p], alveolar [d]~[t], and velar [g]~[k]. To create the continua, the release bursts of the coda stops were first isolated. For the voiced vs. voiceless coda stops at the same place of articulation, bilabial [b]~[p] for example, a five-step continuum was created in Praat using the script created by Mitterer (2009). The items (6)-(8) show the waveforms of the three spectral continua, with the voiced end on top and the voiceless end on bottom.

In the continua, the extremes to the top were the release bursts of the voiced tokens; the other extremes to the bottom were the release bursts of the voiceless tokens. The second to fourth intermediate spectrum steps were processed and generated using the Praat script.

(6) Spectral continuum of bilabial coda stops [b] to [p]

(7) Spectral continuum of bilabial coda stops [d] to [t]

(8) Spectral continuum of bilabial coda stops [g] to [k]

In addition to the release burst, the closure durations of the coda stops were arranged as follows. First, the closure durations in the recording were measured, with the results presented in (9). Second, for stops at the same place of articulation, e.g., [b] vs. [p], the closure duration was set as the mean values of the closure preceding the voiced coda stop (e.g., [b]) and the voiceless one (e.g., [p]), and closure duration values for each voicing pair.

(9) Durations of stop closure in the recordings and their means

Place of articulation of the coda stops	Tokens	Coda stop closure durations as in the recording (ms)	Mean closure durations used in the stimuli (ms)
bilabial	/kæb/ "cab"	78	80
	/kæp/ "cap"	82	
alveolar	/sæd/ "sad"	35	40
	/sæt/ "sat"	44	
velar	/lɒg/ "log"	40	56
	/lɒk/ "lock"	72	

After preparing the continua, the stimulus tokens in the vowel continua (Part 1) were created by compiling a total of 15 (5 steps * 3 continua) stimulus syllables, as detailed in (10). For the CVC syllables containing a bilabial coda stop, continuum (10a) /kæb/~kæp/ for example, the five stimuli contained in a sequence: (i) the same onset consonant [k], (ii) the vowel in five duration steps, (iii) a stop closure with a duration as the mean of that before [b] and [p], and (iv) the same ambiguous release burst between [b] and [p] (i.e., Step 3 of the coda consonant release burst.)

The five tokens with a bilabial coda differed in the duration of the vowel only. A similar arrangement was made for alveolar coda stops and velar coda stops.

(10) Formation of CVC stimulus syllables in the vowel continua (Part 1)
(concatenating onset + vowel duration continuum + stop closure + ambiguous release burst)

	Continuum	Onset	Vowel Duration Continuum	Stop Closure	Ambiguous Release Burst
(a)	/kæX _{bilabial} /	[k]	[æ] _{Step1}	Duration as 80ms (i.e., the mean duration of [b] and [p] in the recordings)	A single ambiguous bilabial coda stop created from [b] and [p]
			[æ] _{Step2}		
			[æ] _{Step3}		
			[æ] _{Step4}		
			[æ] _{Step5}		
(b)	/sæX _{alveolar} /	[s]	[æ] _{Step1}	Duration as 40ms (i.e., the mean duration of [t] and [d] in the recordings)	A single ambiguous bilabial coda stop created from [t] and [d]
			[æ] _{Step2}		
			[æ] _{Step3}		
			[æ] _{Step4}		
			[æ] _{Step5}		
(c)	/lɒX _{velar} /	[l]	[ɒ] _{Step1}	Duration as 56ms (i.e., the mean duration of [k] and [g] in the recordings)	A single ambiguous bilabial coda stop created from [k] and [g]
			[ɒ] _{Step2}		
			[ɒ] _{Step3}		
			[ɒ] _{Step4}		
			[ɒ] _{Step5}		

For the stimulus tokens in the release burst continua (Part 2), a total of 15 (5 steps * 3 continua) stimulus syllables were created, as detailed in (11). For the CVC syllables containing a bilabial coda stop, continuum (11a) /kæb/~kæp/ for example, the five stimuli contained in a sequence: (i) a fixed onset consonant [k], (ii) a fixed ambiguous vowel [æ] with a mean duration taken between /kæb/ and /kæp/ (i.e., Step 3 of the vowel duration continuum), (iii) a fixed stop closure with a duration as the mean of that before [b] and [p], and (iv) a step from the release burst continuum between [b] and [p].

The five tokens with a bilabial coda differed in the release burst quality only. A similar arrangement was made for alveolar coda stops and velar coda stops.

(11) Formation of CVC stimulus syllables in the release burst continua (Part 2)
(concatenating onset + ambiguous vowel + stop closure + release burst continuum)

	Continuum	Onset	Ambiguous Vowel	Stop Closure	Release Burst Continuum
(a)	/kæX _{bilabial} /	[k]	A single ambiguous vowel [æ] created with a mean duration taken between /kæb/ and /kæp/	Duration as 80ms (i.e., the mean across the stop closures of the recordings)	BilabialCoda _{Step1} ([b])
					BilabialCoda _{Step2}
					BilabialCoda _{Step3}
					BilabialCoda _{Step4}
					BilabialCoda _{Step5} ([p])
(b)	/sæX _{alveolar} /	[s]	A single ambiguous vowel [æ] created with a mean duration taken between /sæd/ and /sæt/	Duration as 40ms (i.e., the mean across the stop closures of the recordings)	AlveolarCoda _{Step1} ([d])
					AlveolarCoda _{Step2}
					AlveolarCoda _{Step3}
					AlveolarCoda _{Step4}
					AlveolarCoda _{Step5} ([t])
(c)	/lɒX _{velar} /	[l]	A single ambiguous vowel [ɒ] created with a mean duration taken between /lɒg/ and /lɒk/	Duration as 56ms (i.e., the mean across the stop closures of the recordings)	VelarCoda _{Step1} ([g])
					VelarCoda _{Step2}
					VelarCoda _{Step3}
					VelarCoda _{Step4}
					VelarCoda _{Step5} ([k])

2.2 Experiment procedure

The experiment was hosted on Qualtrics, a professional online survey platform. The anonymous link for access to the online experiment was randomly distributed through social media applications. The true intention of the online experiment was obscured by informing participants that it was designed to assess their ability to correlate English words with their pronunciations.

The participants were invited individually via direct messages on social media platforms such as WhatsApp and Instagram. They were sent a link to the online experiment environment hosted on Qualtrics. Participants completed the experiment with no time constraints. However, they were informed that the optimal completion time was 10 minutes. The procedure in the test phase is exemplified in (12).

(12) Example of the process in the test

The participants were asked to complete the whole experiment process wearing headphones or earphones in a quiet and undisturbed environment. An audio test was set before the test phase of the experiment, and no participants reported hearing impairment or difficulty in listening to the test audio.

Before the test, the participants were instructed to wear their own earphones or headphones, followed by an equipment audio test in which they could press a JavaScript button embedded on the page to play a test audio. This button functioned identically to the test phase audio button, which was used to switch audio sources.

During the test, the participants were then presented with 30 audio clips from the vowel duration continua and release burst continua during the test phase. The sequence of 30 listening instances for each participant was scrambled to force participants to focus on each question rather than predicting the trend of the 5-token continua. They were required to choose one from the two text spelling options, or they could not proceed. The playback of stimuli was controlled by the button programmed using JavaScript, which limited participants to two playbacks of each stimulus. The experiment would conclude if all tasks were completed by the participants.

3. Results

The experiment has successfully collected 25 valid and complete responses. It is estimated that the results were collected from 15 male and 10 female participants. 11 incomplete responses were recorded, and the data collected were excluded from the analysis. Data analysis was conducted using Python 3.13.7 with pandas and AnovaRM libraries. For each acoustic cue (vowel duration and release burst spectrum), separate analyses were performed for each place of articulation (bilabial, alveolar, velar). One-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to test the main effect of step (five steps) on the percentage of voiced responses within each place of articulation. When ANOVA results were significant, post-hoc pairwise comparisons using paired-samples t-tests were conducted to identify specific differences between steps. Bonferroni correction was applied to control for multiple comparisons where appropriate.

3.1 Vowel duration

In vowel duration, the independent variable was the duration steps of the vowels, from short to long. The dependent variable was the participants' judgment of the final coda stop as voiced vs. voiceless. The results for the contrasts in three continua, namely [p]~[b], [t]~[d], and [k]~[g], are presented below.

First, for the effect of vowel duration on coda voicing perception in bilabial stops [p]~[b], participants showed 40.0% voiced responses at the shortest vowel duration at Step 1 (151ms), increasing to 68.0% at Step 4 (253ms), before declining to 52.0% at the longest duration at Step 5 (287ms). However, the overall pattern was not statistically significant ($F(4,120) = 1.034, p = .392$).

- (13) Bilabial coda stops: percentages of responses as [p] (dotted areas) vs. [b] (dark coloured areas) with vowel duration continuum (short to long)

Second, the alveolar stops [t]~[d] demonstrated the most prominent vowel duration effect, with voiced responses increasing from 20.0% ($SD = 40.8%$) at 151ms at Step 1 to 60.0% ($SD = 50.0%$) at Step 5 at 287ms. This pattern yielded a significant main effect of vowel duration ($F(4,120) = 2.537, p = .044$). Pairwise comparisons revealed a significant difference between the shortest and longest vowel durations ($t(24) = -2.828, p = .009$), with longer vowels significantly more likely to be perceived as preceding voiced codas.

- (14) Alveolar coda stops: percentages of responses as [t] (dotted areas) vs. [d] (dark coloured areas) with vowel duration continuum (short to long)

For velar stops [k]~[g], the pattern was similar but less prominent, with voiced responses ranging from 36.0% (Step 1, 151ms) to 60.0% (Step 5, 287ms) across the five duration steps. However, given the fluctuations, this effect was not statistically significant ($F(4,120) = 1.003, p = .409$).

- (15) Velar coda stops: percentages of responses as [k] (dotted areas) vs. [g] (dark coloured areas) with vowel duration continuum (short to long)

3.2 Release burst spectrum

In this section, the independent variable was the coda release burst spectral steps, from a voiced coda to a voiceless one. And the dependent variable was the participants' judgment of the final coda stop as voiced vs. voiceless. The results for the contrasts in three continua, namely [b]~[p], [d]~[t], and [g]~[k], are presented below.

First, for the [b]~[p] continuum, the spectral properties of coda release bursts showed more consistent patterns across places of articulation. For bilabial stops, voiced responses decreased from 48.0% at the voiced burst extreme (Step 1) to 32.0% at the voiceless extreme (Step 5), but this pattern was not statistically significant ($F(4,120) = 0.465, p = .761$).

- (16) Bilabial coda stops: percentages of responses as [b] (dark coloured areas) vs. [p] (dotted areas) with spectral continuum steps of release bursts (Step 1 = [b] and Step 5 = [p])

Second, for the [d]~[t] continuum, the alveolar stops again showed the strongest and most consistent effects. Participants demonstrated 76.0% ($SD = 43.6\%$) voiced responses when presented with voiced-like burst spectra, systematically declining to 16.0% ($SD = 37.4\%$) for voiceless-like bursts. This produced a highly significant main effect ($F(4,120) = 6.660, p < .001$)

and a significant linear trend ($r = -0.904, p = .035$). Pairwise comparisons showed significant differences between Step 1 and Step 5 ($t(24) = 4.243, p < .001$) and between Step 1 and Step 2 ($t(24) = 2.377, p = .026$).

- (17) Alveolar coda stops: percentages of responses as [d] (dark coloured areas) vs. [t] (dotted areas) with spectral continuum steps of release bursts (Step 1 = [d] and Step 5 = [t])

Lastly, the velar [g]~[k] continuum showed a similar decreasing pattern from 56.0% to 40.0% voiced responses across the burst continuum, but this effect did not reach statistical significance ($F(4,120) = 1.030, p = .395$).

- (18) Velar coda stops: percentages of responses as [g] (dark coloured areas) vs. [k] (dotted areas) with spectral continuum steps of release bursts (Step 1 = [g] and Step 5 = [k])

3.3 Summary of cue utilisation

The overall view of the results demonstrated that HKE listeners are able to utilise both temporal and spectral cues for coda voicing perception. Different tendencies were found for the two cues, namely the vowel duration and the coda release burst, but with varying effectiveness depending on the place of articulation of the coda consonant. Diverse patterns were observed in the results of both vowel duration and release burst spectrum.

Alveolar stops consistently showed the strongest effects for both cue types. This suggests that participants were most sensitive to voicing contrasts at this place of articulation. As a spectral cue, burst quality appeared to be more consistently utilised than vowel duration, as evidenced by the clearer linear trends and more robust statistical effects. For the release burst continua, it was unexpected that the participants tended to perceive the release burst quality of the respective coda consonants to be voiceless in general. That being the case, it is suggestive that the Hong Kong English listeners do pay attention to the difference in acoustic properties of the release burst when judging a coda stop as voiceless vs. voiced.

4. Discussion

The above experiment aimed to unveil whether HKE listeners make use of (i) the duration of the preceding vowel and (ii) the spectral property of the coda release burst when identifying a coda stop as voiced vs. voiceless. This section addresses the two research questions in light of these place-specific findings.

4.1 The influence of duration and release burst spectral properties on perceiving coda stop voicing

For the durational effects, it was found that HKE listeners' reliance on temporal cues was limited to alveolar stops. For the alveolar continuum [t]~[d], vowel duration produced a significant main effect ($F(4,120) = 2.537, p = .044$). Pairwise comparisons revealed a reliable increase in voiced responses from the shortest to the longest vowel durations ($t(24) = -2.828, p = .009$). This indicates that listeners are able to exploit temporal information to distinguish [t] vs. [d] when the vowel durations differ sufficiently.

In contrast, bilabial [p]~[b] and velar [k]~[g] continua showed no significant effects (Bilabial: $F(4,120) = 1.034, p = .392$; Velar: $F(4,120) = 1.003, p = .409$). Despite observable percentage changes, these fluctuations did not exceed chance variability. Thus, vowel duration is surprisingly not found as a universally accessible cue for Hong Kong listeners in the current study. Instead, the results suggest that the efficacy of vowel duration in influencing listeners' perception of coda voicing depends on the consonantal context of the coda.

The alveolar-specific effect may reflect articulatory and acoustic salience among the experiment participants. In which the alveolar [t]~[d] pair yields more pronounced temporal differences that are more prominent for the HKE listeners to detect. This aligns with previous findings (Bruggeman et al. 2021) that temporal cues are most salient when paired with acoustically robust consonantal environments.

The release burst spectral cue was likewise found effective only for alveolar stops. The alveolar burst continuum elicited a highly significant effect ($F(4,120) = 6.660, p < .001$) and a strong negative linear trend ($r = -0.904, p = .035$). It indicates that listeners systematically perceived voiceless responses as bursts became more [t]-like. Paired comparisons between the voiced and voiceless extremes confirmed this sensitivity ($t(24) = 4.243, p < .001$).

In contrast, bilabial [p]~[b] and velar [k]~[g] continua yielded non-significant effects (Bilabial: $F(4,120) = 0.465, p = .761$; Velar: $F(4,120) = 1.030, p = .395$). This suggests that spectral distinctions in these positions are less perceptually accessible, possibly due to weaker formant transitions or less salient burst energy differences for the difference in place of articulation of the coda consonant.

Such a pattern in the results for this continuum provided evidence that HKE listeners possess the competence to distinguish coda voicing through specific spectral differences with varied efficacy. This observation only partially matched the previous study (such as Choi et al. 2016) that non-native English users demonstrated a lower sensitivity in perceiving spectral

differences. Yet, the robust alveolar result is also contrary to this conclusion and the general assumptions of the study of Choi et al. (2016) that non-native listeners primarily rely on temporal cues but struggle with spectral cues, given that the tested participants in the current study were able to utilise spectral cues for coda voicing distinctions.

4.2 General discussion

The continuum of the alveolar pair [d]~[t] in the series for the coda release burst spectrum demonstrated favourable results, as a majority of participants selected the correct options in the two extreme steps (in Steps 1 and 5). Additionally, in the continuum of the alveolar pair [t]~[d] in the series for vowel duration, the trend of more participants perceiving the difference and selecting the option corresponding to the voiced end of the continuum (*/sæd/ sad*) was more consistent compared to the other places of articulation for the coda consonant.

Nonetheless, these findings demonstrate that HKE listeners' cue utilisation is not generalised across places of articulation but is constrained to the alveolar context. It indicates the potential of HKE users could have a specific combination of cue usage, and spectral cues can be highly effective when the phonetic context amplifies acoustic contrasts. It highlights the importance of place-specific cue salience in non-native perception. In contrast to Korean non-native English learners in Choi et al. (2016), who relied on temporal cues across all positions, HKE listeners are capable of exploiting both temporal and spectral cues most effectively for alveolar stops. This suggests the possibility that L1-L2 phonological transference operates through context-dependent mapping rather than uniformly across segments.² The effect caused by the difference in L2 exposure should also be considered where possible, as the emphasis imposed on the English language varies between the different societies of Hong Kong and Korea. Further investigation accounting for these sociolinguistic factors is required in further studies.

5. Conclusion

This study attempted to inquire into the perception of HKE listeners on their ability to decode the voicing of the coda stops in words with the simple CVC syllable structure. Specifically, the study attempted to evaluate their ability to perceive the preceding vowel duration, and the burst release quality of the coda stops. This study also attempted to compare the two cues in terms of their prevalence in utilisation when the listeners performed the decoding coda voicing status.

Generally, the experiment results indicated that HKE listeners were able to use both cues in their judgement of coda stop voicing, which differed only in the voicing status of the coda stops. The performance varied in different places of articulation and by different cues. Among the two investigated cues, the experiment yielded strong effects when perceiving alveolar coda consonants instead of reliance on vowel duration or the release burst spectral differences, and the current study informs possible place-specific cue utilisation among HKE users.

For this study, the experiment was conducted in an online environment, which was less controlled and might have diminished the consistency of the environment where the responses were collected. For example, it was unknown whether participants strictly followed the instructions given in the survey introduction to complete the experiment in a quiet environment.

² Cross-linguistic studies such as Du et al. (2022) suggest that coda phonotactic richness in L1 influences L2 cue utilisation. Chinese speakers in the study were found to have more cue restrictions despite their native tonal language experience when compared to Korean speakers. Specifically, Chinese speakers demonstrated significantly smaller vowel duration differences and minimal F0 utilisation.

The attentiveness of the participants was also unknown. Such weaknesses could be eliminated in future studies situated in a lab environment.

Next, the study focused on the majority of HKE listeners who have a Cantonese L1 background, and the language users in Hong Kong with varied L1 backgrounds were not inclusively considered in this study. The language background of the participants of the current study was believed to be relatively more robust, since most of the participants were undergoing university education. This led to an additional weakness in that the findings in this study were generalised with a relatively smaller sample size and a specific group. Hence, the pattern might be different when the same investigation is applied to a larger group of study participants with more diverse language and education backgrounds.

In experiment design, the absence of a native English speaker control group prevented direct performance comparisons and limited conclusions about HKE-specific patterns. Next, the investigation focused exclusively on two acoustic cues (vowel duration and coda release burst duration), while documented research indicates that listeners utilise additional cues. Moreover, the perception-only methodology did not include production tasks using identical CVC stimuli, which prevents analysis of perception-production relationships that could validate participants' cue utilisation strategies. Lastly, cue weighting patterns might be affected by individual difference factors such as English proficiency level and experience, and the length of exposure was not controlled. Further research is needed to examine how HKE listeners use additional acoustic cues to decode coda voicing, and how these cues interact to support their perceptual judgments.

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First Reviewer’s Comments for Yeung’s “Perception of Coda Stop Voicing by Hong Kong English Listeners”

The paper entitled, “*Perception of Coda Stop Voicing by Hong Kong English Listeners*”, is an interesting study. It explores the acoustic cues of (i) pre-consonantal vowel duration and (ii) post-vocalic transient burst of noise that contribute to HKE (Hong Kong English) speakers’ perceptual judgement of [+/-voiced] of the English coda stops, bilabial, alveolar, and velar, in CVC syllables. The study would have been a major contribution to perceptual judgement of voicing of the coda stops in the context of HKE if not for the issues concerning the methodology of the study as given below.

1. The author states that the audio recordings used for the listening tests “*were obtained from the online text-to-speech engine ImTranslator*” (p.4). However, it is unspecified in the paper whether the recordings are synthetic or real speech. There is also a need to examine whether the differences in (i) pre-consonantal vowel duration and (ii) post-vocalic transient burst of noise in the audio recordings are significant between the paired test words, cap/cab, sat/sad, or lock/log, obtained from “*ImTranslator*”. In the paper, the difference in (i) and its significance are presented, but not the difference in (ii).
2. In the paper, there is a lack of information about the creation of the five steps of the spectral continuum of the voiced and voiceless coda stops. It is merely stated that “*a five-step continuum was created in Praat using the script created by Mitterer (2009)*” (p.5). It is unclear how the acoustic attributes of the release burst of the coda stops are manipulated for generating the five steps of the spectral continuum.
3. It is doubtful that the HKE listeners are aware of the difference in coda stop voicing between the paired test words, cap/cab, sat/sad, or lock/log. For the test results to be convincing, prior to the tests the HKE listeners must be screened to prove that (i) they can perceptually distinguish the voiced and voiceless coda stops in the paired test words obtained from the “*ImTranslator*” and (ii) they can correctly produce the voiced and voiceless coda stops when speaking English as do the native speakers of English.

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Second Reviewer's Comments for Yeung's "Perception of Coda Stop Voicing by Hong Kong English Listeners"

This study examines how Hong Kong English (HKE) listeners perceive coda stop voicing in CVC syllables, focusing on two primary acoustic cues: the duration of the preceding vowel and the spectral properties of the coda release burst. The results indicate that both vowel duration and release burst cues play a role specifically in the perception of alveolar stops. This pattern contrasts with the findings reported in Choi et al. (2016), who argued that HKE speakers primarily rely on temporal cues.

The following comments are offered with the goal of helping clarify the analysis and strengthen the overall presentation of the study.

1. Coherence and argumentation

Overall, the paper is clearly written and well-motivated. The discussion of the Cantonese consonantal inventory and contrasts, together with previous empirical findings on non-native English perception, provides a solid foundation for the research questions. In particular, the lack of voicing contrasts in Cantonese and the tendency toward coda neutralization in HKE are well motivated. These questions are addressed through an experimental design that separates temporal and spectral cues. The findings suggest that HKE listeners are able to use both cue types, although their effectiveness depends on place of articulation. This place-specific pattern is an interesting and valuable contribution.

2. Methodology and analysis

The use of Praat scripting to create five-step acoustic continua is appropriate for the goals of the study. The statistical analyses, including repeated-measures ANOVA and Bonferroni-corrected post hoc tests, are generally well chosen and clearly reported.

That said, I had a few questions about certain methodological choices and statistical analysis where additional clarification might help readers better interpret the results:

- a. Stimulus source: The use of a text-to-speech (TTS) engine ImTranslator (Smart Link Corporation 2023) to generate stimuli is understandable given the constraints during the pandemic. However, TTS speech can differ from naturally produced speech in terms of variability and acoustic detail. Since these issues are already acknowledged in the manuscript, a brief discussion of how they might have affected the interpretation of the two cues of interest would further strengthen the study's methodological transparency.
- b. Cue effects across places of articulation & L1 transfer: The results show significant effects for both cues only in the alveolar context (/t/-/d/). I was wondering whether this pattern might be related to different degrees of recognition of Cantonese coda /p, t, k/, and whether this might, in turn, influence how listeners weight voicing cues across different places of articulation. Exploring this possibility, even briefly, could help link the perceptual results more directly to L1 phonological structure.

The author explains in footnote 1 why a native English speaker control group was not included. While this rationale is understandable, future work could consider including unmanipulated English stimuli as a control. Using original English tokens without vowel-duration or release-burst manipulation could help establish baseline recognition rates for English coda /p, b, t, d, k, g/ and clarify whether these baseline patterns contribute to the observed alveolar-specific effect.

- c. English proficiency: The manuscript notes the absence of direct English proficiency measures as a limitation. Given the motivation outlined in the introduction that both Cantonese and Korean lack coda voicing contrasts and that HKE speakers have substantial exposure to English, future work could incorporate a self-rated English proficiency measure to better capture individual differences in L2 experience. From a cue-reweighting perspective, such a measure would make it possible to examine whether increased English experience leads listeners to place greater weight on temporal or spectral cues in coda voicing perception, thereby strengthening the link between the perceptual results and models of L2 speech learning.

In conclusion, the study is carefully conducted and clearly presented. The methodology is transparent, and the place-specific findings regarding cue use provide a meaningful contribution to research on second-language speech perception. With some additional discussion of the points raised above, the paper would be even clearer and more informative for readers.

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